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Glass fiber reinforced plastics (GFRP) waste in wood plastic composites (WPCs)
composition for structural applications

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ABSTRACT

Wind energy is one of the rapidly growing industries of recent times due to global demand of renewable energy. Turbine blade is a key component of wind mill generally made of glass fiber reinforced plastics (GFRP) composites, which do not have proper end-of-life solution due to complex material composition. To solve this problem, feasibility of using demolished wind turbine blade (WTB) waste with different concentrations into wood plastic composites (WPCs) application was investigated. In this research, three different types of WPCs were produced through extrusion technology where solid panels and hollow decks were manufactured to compare them with locally available similar commercial products. Different WPC hollow bars were produced with different WTB composition, recycled plastics and wood pellets to perform material testing. All the experiments followed respective European standards and both mechanical tests (3-point bending and Brinell hardness) were performed by Zwick testing machine before and after immersion for 24 hours and 28 days.

Water soaking test revealed that a hollow bar reference A material absorbed the highest moisture due to high wood content and least by WTB 45% samples where the content of wood was lower. Among all the tested bars, WTB 30% and WTB 45% exhibited better modulus of elasticity (E_{mod}), modulus of rupture (MOR) and Brinell hardness number (BHN) in all conditions. One-way ANOVA test was used to test statistical significance. In deck products tests, Conenor's waste based hollow deck exhibited better MOR, E_{mod} and BHN over UPM ProFi deck before and after 28 day immersion. Similarly, Conenor's composite panel had significantly better mechanical properties over Metsä plywood in all conditions, except lower E_{mod} and MOR in dry condition or before water soaking. Hence, it is suggested to use WTB waste at 30%–45% levels as reinforcement in thermoplastic material composition for extruded composites like bars, panels and multilayer hollow decking aimed for outdoor and other moist applications.

Keywords: GFRP Waste, WTB, extrusion, WPCs, flexural, immersion test

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1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background

Fiber reinforced plastic (FRP) composites have been used extensively for last 30 years as they provide better properties than the products with single materials such as matrix or fibers. The fibers are mostly based on glass, carbon, aramid fibers, and they are reinforced with organic thermoset matrix (e.g. epoxy, polyester) while making FRP composites. Glass fiber reinforced plastics (GFRP) is one of the highly used composite material for various reason such as availability or physical and mechanical properties. Globally, GFRP market is expected to grow at 5.4% rate in between 2015–2020 period (Ribeiro et al. 2016). Only in United States, this consists of 95% among all FRP products and its annual demand has reached to two million metric tons in 2017 (Yazdanbakhsh et al. 2018). They are mainly used in automotive, aerospace, construction as well as in wind turbine system. Furthermore, FRP in turbine blades have increased in recent years due to the increased number of wind energy system around the world.

Wind energy is one of the highly developing renewable energy sources and is expected to fulfil a global electricity demand by 15–18 % by 2050 which is because of rising renewable energy sources. Moreover, European Union has set a goal to produce 20% energy from renewable resources for its member countries by 2020 and therefore wind energy is expected to play a vital role achieving this goal. Recent data has shown that total wind power capacity across whole Europe has reached 173 GW by the end of June 2018 (Cecchinato 2018) which is equal to 12% of total energy demand in the region. This fact also shows the demand for composites which is because more than 90% by weight of turbine blade consists of composite materials. Therefore, more volume of composites in a blade means higher amount of such waste in the future (Liu & Barlow 2017, Jr. et al. 2017). Further, according to Liu & Barlow 2017 and Cherrington et al. 2012 predictions, over 50,000 tons and 200,000-225,000 tons of rotor blade waste will be produced by 2020 and 2034, respectively.

The demand for bio-based materials is rising in manufacturing sectors due to the global concern over environmental challenges. Renewable sources such as wood or their residues can be mixed with thermoplastics or thermosetting plastics to make the products like wood plastics composites (WPCs) which can help to reduce the use of fossil-based materials.

Initially, WPCs were popular among decking applications from extrusion process but growing interest from building and construction have increased the demand in windows, doors and fences as well. Further, products other than extrusion profiles are being made through other process such as injection molding which can make various complex shaped products (Segerholm 2012).

Since this thesis is written for a company Conenor Ltd, extruded panels and profiles will be used in ECOBULK project (Ecobulk 2018) in UK, France, Portugal and particularly in Finland at outdoor bench, shelter and cabin applications for a racing event MOTOGP. This event (MOTOGP world championship) 2020 will be held in Finland after 40 years in Kymiring which is located at 111 km north-east of Helsinki in a town called Kausala. It is believed that promoting such products in these types of event would provide an opportunity to demonstrate the versatile applicability of recycled materials.

1.2 Previous research and gaps in knowledge

Wind turbine blades possess a challenge when it comes to recycling. Majority of rotor blades are made of GFRP composites which are thermosets in nature. Those thermosets cannot be remolded or reshaped once they are heated and hence, it is hard to make recycled products from such plastics. The plastic matrices in blade composition are complex due to variation in size, shape and alignment of fibers which make them hard for recycling (Hoefer 2015). Furthermore, people's perception towards recycled products is not positive as there is a lack of a stricter legislative framework in disposing of recycled (EWEA 2011).

However, legislation towards landfilling of such non-degradable FRP products are getting stricter as some of the European countries have implemented the higher tax or banned in landfilling. This is due to the fact of environmental threat posed by turbine blade's disposal means such as landfill which may release harmful chemicals on earth surface thereby affecting the animals and plants (Hoefer 2015).

Although, numerous researches regarding GFRP waste (e.g. turbine blades) and their recycling can be seen online but still large industrial scale work has not been done yet. Glass fiber wastes are easier to work with mechanical method which allows them to reduce their sizes. For some heavy materials such as turbine blades, grinding is still challenging because of long sizes of blades and cost of making them small before sending them in recycling plant.

More valuable fibers like carbon fibers (CFRP) can be done with chemical or solvolysis methods for fiber extraction but low value products like GFRP needs economically feasible technologies. Further, there is an urgent need of valorization of such products. This research will be focused on wood plastics composites (WPCs) having a reinforcement effect from such type of waste.

1.3 Objectives

The primary aim of this research is to investigate the effect of GFRP composite wastes into wood plastic composites (panels and deck) and to test the products which will be used in shelter or equal structural application.

This research will additionally focus on following areas:

- To test how the differences in concentration of wind turbine blade wastes impacts in wood plastic composite hollow bars compared to their reference products.
- To test the mechanical properties of Conenor's products (panel and deck) and to compare them with commercially available similar products UPM ProFi deck and Metsä Wood Spruce Flex panel.
- To analyze existing end- of- life solutions of such waste composites.
- To use such recycled products (panel and deck) in shelter and other outdoor applications in Kymiring MOTOGP event, 2020 in Finland.

2 LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Overview of composite materials

Composites or composite materials are formed by mixing of two different materials which have different properties thereby providing an entirely new material. Naturally, some of the materials such as wood and bones of human body system are known as natural composites (RSC, 2018). Wood forms through a mixture of cellulose fibers and lignin matrix. Historically, first artificial composite is known as adobe which was made by a mixture of mud and vegetable parts such as straws. In addition, practice of making composite materials have been in human lives for thousands of years for instance, traditional concrete in order to build the houses. Concrete in early days was a mixture of sand and gravels or small stones but in modern days rods are used as well.

During twentieth century, the plastics composites were hugely used, and several construction products were manufactured from materials like glass fiber and polyester (Bai 2013, Thomas 2012). These types of plastic- based composites are highly used in many engineering applications because they are comparatively lighter, stronger, more heterogeneous and durable materials than the traditional materials. Commercially, they are used in transportation, aerospace, construction and automotive sector.

However, composite materials are not all about benefits as there is a serious concern for the environment when it comes to end-of-life (EOL) solution. This is because of inappropriate handling and lack of disposal route. General way of disposing such materials in many countries around the world is still incineration which certainly pollutes the air and land (Giulvezan & Carberry 2003, Moreno 2017).

2.1.1 Global market of composites and wood plastic composites

The global market for composite industry is increasing and is believed to reach €83.17 billion by 2020 which is 40% higher than in 2014 (Job 2016). Further, a market research company based on US has shown that composite market reach to €99.11 billion by 2022 (Mazumdar et al. 2018) and €114.54 billion by 2024. Among all, the biggest production volume is consumed by glass fiber (James 2018). Moreover, use of carbon fibers have skyrocketed at annual rate of 10– 15% per year and this is proven by a fact that only 75,000 metric tons of carbon fibers

were used in 2017. Therefore, more waste can be expected as the demand of such light weight and durable materials are rising especially in transportation, aerospace and construction sector as seen in figure 1.

Figure 1. Global composite end products market size and forecast by application segments (Job 2016).

Like in every other business, composite manufacturing also brings opportunity for other materials than just the fibers. Resin is one of the most essential material for composite industry. When analyzed through total market volume globally, 83.3% share of total resin in 2015 was consumed by thermosetting resin which is because of its advantage in producing stronger products. In addition, thermoplastic resin has also been rapidly growing material in composite business (James 2018).

One can say that composite industry is still in its early stage when it comes to an appropriate end use management if compared to existing materials such as metals which are recyclable up to 80% in contrast to composite's very low. However, the growing support from legislation such as EU's end of life vehicle directive demanding to recycle or to re-use their vehicle parts up to 85% by weight means that manufacturers are obliged to follow the approach of circular economy (Black 2017) and thereby helping in reducing the amount of waste.

A data published in EU statistics 2010 has shown that a single person produces 6 tons waste out of 16 tons consumption per year. In total, 34.7% of the wastes are mainly from construction and demolition whereas 28.2% comes generates from mining and geological extraction as well as 10% from manufacturing industries (Keskisaari 2018).

Global WPCs market

The total value of a worldwide WPC market was estimated at \$4.01 billion (€3.61 bn) in 2017 with an annual rising at 9.3% and is expected to reach \$8.15 billion (€7.18 bn) by 2025 (Grandview 2018). In contrast, a report from US based Zion market research has claimed that global market for WPCs will increase at annual rate of 12.3% during the time period 2017-2022 and is forecasted to be at \$8.76 billion (€7.72 bn) by 2022. In 2016, the total volume of such materials production was about 4,262.3 kilotons globally (Dorothyzmr 2017). With those figure, one can easily predict that WPCs market is rising high.

The main application areas of WPCs are construction and building where typical decking products are popular among manufacturers as shown in figure 2. In addition, application in interior parts of automotive industry as well as consumer goods have become important application areas for WPCs materials.

Figure 2. Application fields of WPC in Europe in 2012 (Carus et al. 2015).

In terms of global market volume, WPCs market growth was rapid in both North America and China in between 2010–2015 time period as seen in figure 3. But, China’s growth in WPCs became largely popular and hence, overcoming North America’s production volume by 2015.

Figure 3. Total volume of WPCs in different parts of the world (Sommerhube 2015).

When analyzed total WPCs volume (2010, 2012 and 2015 period), North America was a global leader in WPCs market until 2012 but China progressed rapidly after 2012 thus, leaving North America behind them, as shown in figure 3.

China basically uses polyethylene (PE) or polyvinylchloride (PVC) based polymer matrix in their WPCs products and most of the products are based on these thermoplastic polymer matrices. For the last decade, Chinese WPC market based on those two plastics reached 1,540,000 tons in 2015 thereby making a growth rate of 7%. They are a powerhouse when it comes to WPC research and developments in the world as more than half of the entire patents belongs to them. It is estimated to be over 100 million tons (valued \$200 billion being ca. €176.30 bn) of WPCs are produced only in China at the moment which is because of high market demand. In contrast, Europe has comparatively small market size and growth rate compared to China (only 260,000 tons of WPCs in 2012 as shown in figure 2).

The newest development and finding new areas of applications such as interior design for households, hotels as well as automotive applications like high-speed trains need more of these products. Moreover, technological advancement in processes such as co-extrusion which allows using multiple materials gives different products. Similarly, WPCs in hybrid

designs with other materials such as steel or aluminum have created new market areas (Song 2016).

2.2 Wood plastic composites (WPCs)

Wood plastic materials are composed of two or more than two materials consisting wood fibers/flour, plastics and additives. WPC is a term which can be described broadly where either thermoplastics or thermosets plastics are used along with wood. Moreover, other natural fibers like hemp, jute, kenaf, rice husks etc. are being used as natural fiber composites (NFCs). Additives are other components used in WPCs, these can be for instance colorant, fillers, lubricants, UV-stabilizers, biocides, compatibilizers and coupling agents. Often, virgin materials are used in commercial scale production but waste stream from both plastic and wood industries can also be used in manufacturing process. These can be for instance, saw dust from lumber manufacturing and plastic pellets from plastic industries (Liukko et al. 2007, Segerholm 2012, Toghiani 2017).

Plastic matrix is a key component in WPCs which holds and binds the different components. This also helps to minimize the water absorption of wood thereby making it mold and rot resistant. In contrast, wood flour acts as filler and gives better elastic modulus and flexural strength (Chaudemanche et al. 2018). In general, thermoplastics are more common in WPCs than thermosets. Further, polyethylene-based thermoplastics are even more popular among WPCs production than the polymer matrix such as polypropylene (PP) and polyvinyl chloride (PVC) (Grandview Research 2018).

A study by Spear (2015) revealed that countries like Germany are utilizing agricultural residue, for instance rice husk, as filler instead of wood fiber and dust. This is because of such materials are locally available in many countries and they can be used as filler for WPC production. At the same time, use of WPC products has increased in recent times.

However, the most common types of wood used in WPCs are maple, pine and oak which is because of their availability in various region around the world whereas thermoplastics such as polyethylene (PE), Polypropylene (PP), Polyvinyl chloride (PVC) and Polystyrene (PS) are commonly used. Further, plastic raw material for WPC have also been used from waste stream such as municipal solid waste (MSW) since 1990s and their use is rising due to favoring

legislation and environmental issues (Najafi 2013). Moreover, recycled materials are cheaper to get, and this prevents them from disposing.

The first application of WPCs was used in automotive sector until 1990s when it was recognized in international market for decking products. Later, the focus was well distributed to other products such as fences and frames for housing as well as other building applications as shown in figure 4–5. WPCs can be produced through various methods depending upon the desired dimensions. The description of different production methods is explained in further headings (Segerholm 2012, Liukko et al. 2007).

Figure 4. WPC decking and housing application (Alibaba 2018).

Figure 5. Various consumer product applications of WPCs (Wang 2015).

2.2.1 Methods of WPC production

Main raw materials for WPC production are thermoplastics polymers along with lignocellulose-based materials or natural fibers. Besides, different additives are added to enhance the properties. Wood is a major source of lignocellulosic material where different form of wood such as pellets, flour or particles are used. On the other hand, thermoplastic polymers such as PE, PP, HDPE, PS and PVC are used in addition to the different additives. Various methods have been employed in WPC processing as shown in figure 6.

Figure 6. General processing of WPC (Martikka 2013, Vilkki 2019).

Processing of wood raw materials can be done either by compounding step or as a direct extrusion of profiles in addition to the agglomeration followed by extrusion. Some of the most common methods are explained below.

Extrusion

Most of the WPC products are made with extrusion process because of its wide range of applications in decking, fencing, planks and siding products. Extrusion produces continuous linear profiles and key component of the processing system is extruder where mixing (plastics, wood and additives) and heating takes place before feeding them into die located at the end of the extruder. The die is also an important part of the system as it gives the dimension and the shape to the final product. Once the product is formed, cooling takes place in a cooling tank and the profiles rolls into rolling table for further cooling and to cut- off saw (Wang 2015, Schwarzkopf and Burnard 2016).

In this study, Conenor's CONEX® CWE 500-2 extruder as shown in figure 7, was used to produce multilayer composite deck samples.

Figure 7. Illustration of multilayer profile CONEX® CWE 500-2 extrusion line (Conenor 2018).

In recent times, majority of continuous profiles are made through direct extrusion system (one- step process) where profiles can be either solid or hollow shaped. In addition, extrusion

can take through different types of system for WPC profiles such as single screw, co-rotating twin screw, counter rotating twin screw and woodtruder system (Wang 2015).

Injection molding

This method is typically used to make products with complex 3D- geometries. Similar to extrusion, mixing and feeding of materials to the hopper takes place in the beginning. Further, melting, shaping and cooling takes place before it comes out as a product. However, injection molding requires mold to fill with molten mixtures instead of die in extrusion which gives the desired shaped products (Akinfiresoye et al. 2017).

Compression molding or thermoforming

Compression molding or thermoforming along with injection molding in WPC manufacturing are used when more complex or different products than continuous profiles are needed to produce. This method is highly used in automobile parts manufacturing industry (Wang 2015).

Other new technologies and developments

Apart from above mentioned methods, some authors like Rowell (2013) and Sercer et al. (2009) have mentioned calendaring method to manufacture WPCs where molten materials are fed in between calendars instead of die or mold halves.

In addition, wet process is also used to make sheets of WPCs which are being used by automotive industry. In this method, semi-liquid formation is made from water and wood mixture where additives will be added before pressing them by hot press to form sheet product. Further, 3D printing is another method of WPC production where fused deposition modelling (FDM) that is popular among researchers, hobbyist and small manufacturers to play with different materials and methods (Schwarzkopf and Burnard 2016).

New manufacturing methods are also being applied in WPCs production such as coextrusion, where a co-extrusion die with multiple extruders is processing multiple materials simultaneously. This process is already familiar among fencing producers and is expected to be used even more by decking manufacturers, as Chinese decking producers have already started using co-extruded PVC based WPCs in curtain, wall and windows (Song 2016). The Conenor invented multilayer CONEX[®]-extruder utilizes a simple die to form the multilayer product shape fed with 2 individually operated rotors nested inside each other. The main

benefit of the CONEX®-extruder is that both material layer formulations, product inside and outside, can be freely chosen in optimization of the product cost and performance while in co-extrusion the outer material layer must be always plastic rich with less reinforcing fibers (Conenor 2018). Similarly, foaming during extrusion makes foamed WPCs and they are often light weight and have a better impact resistance. Moreover, coatings with latex paints or polyurethanes in WPCs are being used for better look and to increase durability but coating must be done before they reach to customers. There is still lack of efficient surface treatment methodology (Faruk & Sain 2015).

2.2.3 Waste materials in WPC application

Plastics are one of the major global environmental concern over recent times (Ashori & Nourbakhsh 2009) and recycling of such materials provide less environmental impact thereby saving virgin raw materials. In wood plastic composites, virgin thermoplastics such as PE, PP, PVC and PS are highly used in addition to the fiber or wood as filler material along with small quantities of additives. However, due to technological development recycled thermoplastics has also been utilized as a raw material source for WPCs because of their low- cost and the availability in large volume (Najafi 2013). Further, there is also evidence where recycled plastics are suggested to use in WPCs which not only protects the environment but also creates value to the product. The application of such products (a shown in figure 8), for instance park benches, floor parquet and picnic tables. Kärki & Martikka (2019) and Tabarsa et al. (2011) have mentioned in their research that the use of recycled plastic in WPC possess better properties than that of virgin plastics.

Figure 8. Multilayer WPC profiles made of recycled materials in Conenor Ltd.

In addition, due to the advancement in conversion technologies, development of new materials is getting more feasible. This research is one of the examples where waste materials from composite and plastic industry are converted into WPCs.

2.3 Fiber reinforced plastic (FRP) composites

In modern world, thermoset based FRP is being widely used in many different sectors such as automotive, aerospace, and marine and construction. Fiber reinforced plastic (FRP) is a composite material where fibers and plastics matrix are mixed together to make desired products. Fibers are generally glass fiber, carbon or polyethylene (PE) whereas plastics matrix can be thermosetting resin, or thermoplastics.

The molecular chain of thermoplastics matrices is formed by weak Van der Waals forces and therefore those molecular bonds break and reconnect upon heat and cooling, respectively. This property makes them easier when it comes recycling. In contrast, thermosetting resin cannot be re-melted and reformed due to the cross-linking mechanism which makes them strong. In addition, fibers and matrix are two key components of fiber reinforced composites where matrix behaves as a dominant over fibers due to its wider role in composite formation. Matrix protects fibers, transfer stresses in between them as well as to change the location in order to produce the rigidity to final products. In contrast, fiber contributes in providing strength and stiffness to the final product (Uddin 2013, Masuelli 2013). In another words, this can also be illustrated as composite formation by two or more phases where matrix acts as a

primary phase which is a continuous in character and secondary is dispersed phase (reinforcing), discontinuous. Composites can be further classified into three subgroups based on their phases as shown in figure 9.

Figure 9. Two phases of composite formation (Sabu Thomas 2012).

Reinforcing composite materials make them better in terms of stiffness and strength when compared to its original structure. One can easily predict that strength of only polymer-based materials have lower strength than that of reinforced materials. In general, composites possess a strong quality over traditional materials and sometimes composites perform even better than existing metals or glasses. Properties of such composites depends on balance between matrix and reinforcing materials (Bai 2013). The structure of composites is not always the same even though they look similar and they are typically in the form of layers, grains and fiber as shown in figure 10.

Figure 10. Fiber structures in composites.

The common issue with composite is often exaggerated to be highly expensive but due to their excellent properties as well as the increasing demand, high volume production is being done which is helping to reduce the costs. The composites are generally low in density, high stiffness, better against corrosion and good thermal insulation.

The studies have found that global demand for only natural fiber composites have reached US \$ 2.1 billion in 2010 and are even increasing higher due to the widened application areas. One of the common examples of composites can be taken as wood plastic products in China which is rising high at the rate of 30% per year. This is due to the fact that increasing awareness towards environmental issues as well as availability of such materials. The most commonly used fibers are jute, flax, sisal, hemp as well as residues from paddy field, pineapple leaf and oil palm are used extensively (Uddin 2013).

Due to the advancement in technology and advantageous characters, FRP composites are slightly replacing traditional materials for building and construction such as concretes and steel. In addition, they also possess a great strength, light weight and non- corrosive in nature. There are several types of FRP composites available in the market for instance carbon fiber, Kevlar, PE and so on. But glass fiber or fiber glass is the most common fiber reinforced composite available due to its cost factor and availability.

2.3.1 Glass fiber reinforced plastic (GFRP) composites

Glass fiber is one of the highly used and most versatile plastics matrix composites in FRP where about 90% of the total FRP products are made of GFRP materials. Mostly they are composed of thermosetting resin because of their advantageous features. Thermosets such as epoxy, polyester and vinyl ester are common and in reality, most of GFRP products in market are totally based on those thermoset matrix (Garcia et al. 2014).

GFRP products can be divided into two categories, low cost and premium product. The low cost such as E-glass and is often considered as the oldest type of fiber glass, whereas premium class glass fibers, for instance S-glass are mostly used in aviation business (Wallenberger et al. 2001, Mallick 2007). S- glass have higher tensile strength and modulus of elasticity than E-glass and therefore it is more attractive to aerospace sector. Furthermore, there are also other categories of glass fibers barely used in real life such as C- glass, A- glass, D- glass, R-glass and so on. Main chemical components in all glass fibers typically consists of silica (SiO_2)

and oxides (e.g. magnesium, aluminum, barium etc.). Table 1 and table 2 show the chemical composition and properties of the different types of glass fibers (Prashanth et al. 2017).

Table 1. Chemical composition (by weight %) of glass fiber types

Type	(SiO ₂)	(Al ₂ O ₃)	TiO ₂	B ₂ O ₃	(CaO)	(MgO)	Na ₂ O	K ₂ O	Fe ₂ O ₃
E-glass	55.0	14.0	0.2	7.0	22.0	1.0	0.5	0.3	–
C-glass	64.6	4.1	–	5.0	13.4	3.3	9.6	0.5	–
S-glass	65.0	25.0	–	–	–	10.0	–	–	–
A-glass	67.5	3.5	–	1.5	6.5	4.5	13.5	3.0	–
D-glass	74.0	–	–	22.5	–	–	1.5	2.0	–
R-glass	60.0	24.0	–	–	9.0	6.0	0.5	0.1	–
EGR-glass	61.0	13.0	–	–	22.0	3.0	–	0.5	–
Basalt	52.0	17.2	1.0	–	8.6	5.2	5.0	1.0	5.0

Table 2. Physical and mechanical properties of the glass fiber types

Fiber	Density (g/cm ³)	Tensile strength GPa	Young's modulus (GPa)	Elongation (%)	Coefficient of thermal expansion (10 ⁻⁷ /°C)	Poisson's ratio	Refractive index
E-glass	2.58	3.445	72.3	4.8	54	0.2	1.558
C-glass	2.52	3.310	68.9	4.8	63	–	1.533
S ₂ -glass	2.46	4.890	86.9	5.7	16	0.22	1.521
A-glass	2.44	3.310	68.9	4.8	73	–	1.538
D-glass	2.11–2.14	2.415	51.7	4.6	25	–	1.465
R-glass	2.54	4.135	85.5	4.8	33	–	1.546
EGR-glass	2.72	3.445	80.3	4.8	59	–	1.579
AR glass	2.70	3.241	73.1	4.4	65	–	1.562

Glass fibers possess properties like high strength, stiffness, flexibility, electrical insulation and chemical resistant. Therefore, people have been using them since ancient times such as Egyptians have made containers from glass fibers. In addition, electrical appliances were made in 1930s when people developed the continuous glass fibers. Current market for GFRP composite is over \$42.01 billion (ca. €37.40 bn) in 2017 and this is rising at annual rate of 7.5% and this would make the value worth of \$80.57 billion (ca. €70.01 bn) by 2026. One of the key reasons in inflation of such products are because of rising automotive industries and high use of GFRP in Asian market condition (Sathishkumar et al. 2014, Reuters 2018). Despite having huge market potential, feasible EOL solution has always been an issue for FRP composites. Some of the treatment methods are explained below.

There are few recycling methods of GFRP composites have been discovered. Firstly, mechanical way which involves shredding into smaller pieces and secondly thermal degradation by pyrolysis method which degrades matrices by heating. Thirdly, fiber recovery

is done through a chemical degradation method where chemical liquids break down the matrices. This method is popular in CFRP fiber recovery process but not preferred to glass fibers due to the cost as a limiting factor. For GFRP waste, mechanical way of recycling is considered most suitable. Furthermore, energy recovery method is little debatable because of involvement of incineration, which makes air pollution (Wait 2010). In addition, a study done by Mativenga & Shuaib (2010) have noted some additional ways to recover GFRP composites such as fluidized bed method, high voltage fragmentation and microwave pyrolysis.

GFRP composite waste

Due to high use of FRP materials in many sectors such as wind, construction and building, huge amount of waste is being produced. Therefore, recycling has been an important topic of discussion in recent times because of increasing concern over environment protection but at the same time headache for many industries due to the legislations favoring recycling over traditional landfilling and incineration. Studies have shown that GFRP waste is being incinerated or ending up in landfill due to difficulties in recycling issues.

This is because of two reasons; firstly, the crosslinking nature of thermosets which makes them hard to breakdown. Secondly, GFRP is made with several components such as plastics (e.g. glass fibers), additives and inorganic fillers which make them more complex structure and therefore they are hard to recycle (Ribeiroa et al. 2013). Further, such traditional method of disposal comes at high cost for instance, FRP waste management cost in US was \$45–\$200 (ca. €53–235) per ton in 2014 whereas in UK (Brown et al. 2018) £140 (ca. €164) per ton for either to dispose or to landfill. When managing FRP waste, sometimes materials like GFRP are easy to reuse in many applications such as slabs or any flat works depending upon its suitability.

There are basically two ways of FRP recycling mechanism, the first one is mechanical way which involves shredding, crushing and milling. Second method is, fiber recovery from polymer matrix, and this is often expensive and applicable to carbon fibers but not for glass fibers. Therefore, high value products like CFRP are treated with this process. Recycling GFRP composites is challenging due to their high resistance towards chemical and thermal condition. However, it has also techniques for them to recycle through cement kiln route,

which is also supported by EU legislation. In this process, GFRP- waste are reduced their sizes, fed them into cement clinker to produce cement (Backer 2011, Yazdanbakhsh & Bank 2014, Yazdanbakhsh et al. 2018). However, it is stressed that cement kiln processing is not a circular method, instead this can be considered as EOL solution for GFRP-waste. Moreover, the type of cement produced in cement kiln process utilizing GFRP waste has different properties compared to the existing cement qualities and therefore, this can have only limited market.

GFRP materials have great mechanical properties as well as durability despite having their shorter lifespan for functional or design reason. In the United States, majority of GFRP waste are dumped into landfill as they are non-biodegradable and hard for further treatment. This is because of most of GFRP made from thermoset plastics (75%) which is hard to melt even at high temperature (Yazdanbakhsh et al. 2018). Further, cross linking makes them hard to remold.

The major route of disposing GFRP composite waste is still landfilling and incineration. In Japan, estimated amount 400,000 tons of waste GFRP were fed into landfill and incinerated where only few amounts were used for fuel and concrete manufacturing industries (Aono et al. 2011). The similar situation exists in UK as well (Mativenga & Shuaib 2010). United States (US) too has a difficulty in dealing with GFRP waste, but they have recently formed an organization called IACMI in the field of composite, aims to recycle composite materials by 80% by next decade. Further, some of the European countries like Germany and Holland have already initiated restricting landfilling and therefore it is expected to see other countries following them in near future (Yazdanbakhsh et al. 2018)

Several researches have shown that GFRP waste has possibilities in different applications. For example, some have used GFRP chips for bathtubs making and some used them for concrete and cement production. Further, this can also act as a filler or reinforcement and some people use it for artificial wood. Moreover, this is also used in plastics - concrete materials (Yazdanbakhsh et al. 2018, Ribeiroa et al. 2013, Aono et al. 2011, Mativenga & Shuaib 2010).

There is an immense pressure for researchers to make valuable products from such waste types. Since the thermal or chemical way of fiber recovery from GFRP composite do not seem viable, mechanical way of treatment is only a better solution for its end use application. Moreover, there are numerous studies available where mechanically grinded GFRP waste are

used to make products like Portland cement concrete (Ribeiro et al. 2016). Author has also learned from the composite seminar in Lahti Finland, 2018 that GFRP composite waste (e.g. turbine blades) are being used in cement kiln industry in Germany.

2.4 Wind energy and the turbine blade

Due to the global concern over fossil- based energy, focus has been given to the renewable sources such as hydro, geo, biomass and wind sources to fulfil the energy demand. Wind energy is one of the rapidly growing renewable energy sources of last two decades. In the US, wind energy production in 1999 was 30 times less than the current situation whereas in China, this has been even higher. EU also predicts that wind energy consumption will rise from 5.3% in 2010 to 15.7% in 2020. In addition, a review by Liu & Barlow (2017) mentioned two predictions where first data by European wind energy association predicting 14.9% of electricity by 2020 whereas international energy association estimates 15–18% of the total global energy (electricity) is expected to be fulfilled by wind energy by 2050.

The statistical data by global wind energy council shows that global installed wind power capacity by 2017 was 539,581 MW in contrast to the 39,062 MW in 2010 and 8,133 MW in 2003. The dominance of such energy production is clearly seen in Asia due to the rising economy of countries like China and India (Beauson et al. 2016, GWEC 2018, Yazdanbakhsh et al. 2018). In Europe too, use of composites in wind energy system has been increased as seen in figure 11 where, only 50,000 tons of composites were used in 2000s, but the amount was reached in between 110 k tons and 140 k tons after 10 years period (2010).

Figure 11. Annual use of FRP composites in wind turbine blades in Europe (EWEA 2011).

More recently, Kallio (2017) has noted that estimated 77,000 turbines in Europe with the total capacity of 153.7 GW in 2016 where, not only onshore but also offshore wind energy is expected to increase (21% annually) (Jr. et al. 2017). Power of each turbine varies if it is onshore or offshore where each onshore turbine may produce about 2.7 MW and offshore can produce about 5.6 MW power. To the date, 9 MW capacity with 88.4 m long blade wind turbine is considered as biggest in terms of power and size (Kallio 2017) whereas Messaoudi (2018) has noted, Adwen AD 180 Bremerhaven's 89 meter long blade is longest ever by the end of 2017. But, a recent report by Kellner (2019) has mentioned that largest wind turbine blade (107 m) is longer than a football field, made of wood, carbon fibers and glass fibers. It is also believed to power 16,000 homes. The competition over longer turbine blades to generate more electricity indicates that companies are trying to produce energy at lower cost, thus increasing the blade length. This means, more GFRP waste will be produced when they come to end of their service lives.

In a Finnish case scenario, the total amount of wind turbines was 700 by the end of 2017 which has produced 2044 MW of energy, thereby contributing 5.6% of total energy. Further, there are also additional projects which aimed to produce 2000 MW electricity in coming

years. To begin this, 15 projects were announced in early April 2018 which are going to produce 500 MW of electricity (Suomen tuulivoimayhdistys 2017).

Denmark is one of the pioneer countries in the world when it comes to the wind energy. The country has installed a lot of onshore and offshore wind turbines which can also easily be seen their capital as shown in figure 12. In addition, figure 13 shows the several components of the entire wind energy system.

Figure 12. Offshore wind turbine system in Copenhagen, Denmark (photo taken in 2018).

Figure 13. Wind turbine components (UKA Group 2018).

Historically, turbine blade for wind energy was made of steel which failed initially but worked later during 1941's in Vermont, US. After that, wind turbine was built in Gedser, Denmark in 1956 – 1957 where composite structure was used by steel bars, wood and aluminum shells. In addition, some of the developing countries like India are still using wood in remote part of the country for a small - scale turbine system. This is because of availability of such natural composites as well as the low materials cost. The commercialization of modern kind composite rotor blades in wind energy system was started only in 1988 – 1989 from both US and Denmark (Jr. et al. 2017, Maskepatil et al. 2014).

The main function of wind turbine is to produce energy from air, and this involves kinetic energy conversion into electrical power. The amount of electricity production depends on how fast rotor blade rotates based on the wind speed but not how much is the demand. Whole system is made of many different parts such as gear box, blade hub, blades and tower. The turbine blades and nacelles are usually made with GFRP composites whereas hub, gear box and tower are made of metals. In general, metals are easier to recycle but components like turbine blades are a serious concern due to their composition (as shown in figure 14) and

difficulties of recycling (Kalagi et al. 2016). In contrast, Liu & Barlow (2017) have mentioned turbine's main components such as turbine blade (90% composite), concrete foundation, metallic nacelle and tower made of steel or concrete.

Figure 14. Material composition of a turbine blade (WindEurope 2017).

There are three rotor blades in a turbine blade and their sizes have been drastically increased from 12–15 meter in an early stage up to 90 meter and beyond in modern blades. They are not changed only in size and design but also improved their composition and capacity. Those early days blades in 1990s had less power (600 kW) when compared to that of new version of such blades containing 7 MW. Moreover, lifespan of such old turbine blade is estimated to be around 20–25 years and now time has come for their end of life. However, recently made turbine blades may have better features due to the technological advancement than previous models which would help them stay longer (Marsh 2017, Brondsted 2016).

Manufacturing methods of turbine blades can be different from one to another. Some of them are for instance, hand layup or vacuum assisted hand layup (laminating technique) where fibers are kept in various layers in the mold surface before impregnating them with resin. Similarly, fibers are fed through a resin bath to the rotating mandrel in filament winding process. This method is also popular among cylindrical components manufacturing industry.

Further, resin infusion or vacuum resin infusion (VARTM, SCRIMP) is a process where vacuum is used to suck the resin from vacuum bag. This method along with blade infusion are useful for larger components manufacturing even if the entire process is little challenging. In contrast, when fibers are pre-impregnated with partially cured resin, vacuum bagged and heat is applied, the method belongs to the prepreg technology and this in fact is a much clean and safe technique (Aymerich 2012, Nolet 2011). Prepreg methods are adapted from aviation industry and they are fairly expensive than infusion process, but products are better with this. However, both are equally considered as contributing technologies for improving quality (Jr. et al. 2017).

The modern turbine blades are made with polymer composites (e.g. GFRP) reinforcement as shown in figure 14. FRP materials in such composition are mostly thermosets in nature, and they undergo crosslinking during curing process. The reinforcing fibers are mostly glass fibers but also carbon fibers, aramids or basalt fibers, which consists of 60 – 70% of total weight of the blade, are used. Further, plastic matrix or resin, such as epoxies, polyesters, polyurethane and vinyl consist of 30–40% of total volume. Furthermore, there are also minor fractions of metals attached and the blades are coated with either polyethylene or polyurethane plastics. This makes blade more powerful in terms of strength as well as provides resistance to fatigue, corrosion and thermal conductivity (WindEurope 2017, Cecchinato 2018).

2.4.1 Recycling of turbine blades

Since the first-generation turbine blades are approaching end of their lifespan, it is estimated that about 50,000 tons of waste will be collected globally within next two years period, 200,000 tons by 2034 (Barlow 2014) and a massive 43 million tons by 2050 (Liu & Barlow 2017). As shown the projection trend in figure 15, growth volume of wind turbines is expected to grow steadily for few decades in contrast to their highly increasing end of life amounts.

In addition, blade wastes are not only being produced from the EOL of blades, but also significant amount of waste are produced from manufacturing blades. Most recent annual report from one of the largest wind energy producers, Vestas, has noted that 81,000 tons of waste was produced in 2018, where only 42,000 tons was collected for recycling (Vestas 2018).

Figure 15. Annual wind turbine blade waste projection globally (Liu & Barlow 2017).

Therefore, recycling is an important issue to deal with. In an entire turbine system, only 10–15% by mass is consumed by blade which means 6 - 8 tons weight for a 1.5 MW power turbine. In 2016, it was estimated that 150,000–190,000 tons of FRP are stored in such blades in Europe and this may go as waste in the future (Kallio 2017). Furthermore, another study has pointed out that average capacity of a turbine will be 10 MW in between 2020–2030 and one can predict that size of blades will be increased. For a 2 MW turbine, it is estimated that mass (in tons) of major components such as tower, nacelle, hub, gearbox and blades are 143, 2.3, 13, 16 and 19.5 tons, respectively (Andersen et al. 2014).

The entire turbine components are made with different materials and each of them have separate recycling routes. Flow- chart in table 3 shows components and their end of life route:

Table 3. Components of turbine blades and their end of life route (Albers 2009)

Wind turbine components		Trends in end of life solution
Foundation (Concrete/steel)		Building material recycling
Tower (Coated steel)		Steel recycling/scrap
Generator and drive train (Metallics)		Material recycling/reprocessing
Electronics (cable, switches)		Recycling/reprocessing
Rotor blade and nacelle (Fiber composite and metals)		Incineration, landfilling, recycling (metals only).

Simply, there are two ways to deal with waste. Firstly, waste is disposed into landfill sites, burnt in power plants or secondly use recycling method. In this case, typical way to get rid of such waste are to be landfilling but due to the law restriction and high cost of doing so, recycling is inevitable. In EU, landfill cost of waste blades is 100–250 €/ton and incineration would cost 170 €/ton. But if it is handed to the cement manufacturers, they would take shredded FRPs at about 160 €–190 €/ton which is even better and cheaper option than to landfill them (Kallio 2017).

The majority of turbine blades are composed of glass fiber composites and in rare cases, carbon fibers have also been used. GFRP being comparatively cheaper, stronger and easy availability makes them first choice over other materials.

However, recycling is not being done as efficiently as it should be when compared to other components of wind turbine system. The difficulties in recycling are for instance, due to the complexity of composite materials used in rotor blades. Sometimes, impurities in turbine blades such as metallics as shown in figure 16, may disturb the recycling process (Kallio 2018).

Figure 16. Impurities in turbine blade (Kallio 2018).

There is a belief that recycling issue is not being done due to lack of technologies but by other reasons such as high investment and processing cost which would make them even expensive than the pristine glass fibers. Some of the mechanism have already been developed for instance, thermal process including pyrolysis, fluidized bed thermal process and microwave pyrolysis methods.

Pyrolysis decomposes organic particles in an inert environment in presence of high temperature (300–370°C) whereas fluidized bed operates even at higher temperature, around 450°C and this is one of the most researched method (Andersen et al. 2014). Moreover, recycling in mechanical method involves grinding and shredding for size reduction allows them to substitute filler elements in molding applications. But thermal and thermo-chemical processes are considered as recovery methods for energy recovery such as heat electricity and fuel. Some of the general methods of handling composite waste are presented in figure 17.

Figure 17. Disposal and recycling options for blades (EWEA 2011).

There is also evidence of waste GFRP ashes being used in concrete industry (Fox 2016). Lägerdorf cement plant is a company located in Germany uses the decommissioned turbine blades for both fuel and raw material in a cement production. GFRP composites produce ash upon incineration which partly replaces the sand that is needed for cement production (Andersen et al. 2014).

2.4.2 Alternative materials for turbine blade

Selection of material for turbine blade is always a key aspect which is directly related to the cost and durability. Issue related to the current form of turbine blades are because of thermoset materials in their composition which, many believed are hard or cannot be recycled. On the other hand, making blades with other materials may cost higher price, low strength and fatigue properties. There have been numerous amounts of studies and experiments done if the existing blades can be replaced in an efficient way for instance by using thermoplastics which are more environmentally friendlier than thermosets (Thomas & Ramachandra 2018). Table 4 analyses the trends in possible alternatives for blade composition rather than GFRP.

Table 4. Possible alternative materials for wind turbine blades (Jr. et al. 2017, Thomas & Ramachandra 2018)

Materials	Characteristic features
Natural fiber composites (NFCs)	They have high mechanical properties, non-toxic, non-abrasive environmentally friendly (CO ₂ neutral) and easily available as species like bamboo can be found anywhere in the world. This can best fit to developing countries where small scale turbines can be set onsite even in a low budget. Research have shown that bamboo, flax, wood (birch) were used in composite formation for wind blades.
Thermoplastics	They may not be as strong as thermosets, but thermoplastics have higher fracture toughness, they are recyclable and repaired because of their phase changing property with temperature change. Research (Kumar et al. 2013) has shown that thermoplastic FRP are weaker in strength (7–8 times) than thermosets but use of alternative thermoplastics such as polyetherimide, polyetheretherketone, polyphenylene sulfide and anionic polyamide- 6 shows better strength.
Hybrid composite	Hybrid reinforcement provides an alternative to glass and carbon fibers. This sort of composite is suitable for light weight blade where materials such as hemp and jute (natural fibers) are used. Studies have shown that glass fibers incorporation into carbon fibers improves the impact properties. Longer type turbine blade (88.4 m) from LM Wind power is an example of such composite.
Nano compound plastics	By adding nano reinforcement such as carbon nanotubes (CNT)/Nano clay into resin provides better stiffness and toughness than to the virgin resin. Studies have shown that addition of 1–5 wt.% carbon nanofibers into glass fibers reinforced epoxy composite in turbine blade manufacturing provides increased tensile stress and modulus.
Aramid and basalt fibers	Aramid is a non - glass aromatic polyamide which has high mechanical strength and toughness but are weak against UV and moisture. In contrast, basalt fibers possess better mechanical properties than regular E- glass. Some experiments were carried out with basalt fibers in a hybrid material with carbon fiber in small- scale turbine blade manufacturing.

However, challenge of finding perfectly fit material and to design the blade accordingly to produce light weight, strong, durable, cost effective and environmentally friendly blades can be considered as the best-case scenario for future. In some cases, new approaches are being applied such as 3D printing method for gas turbine blade which produces sharp cutting edges in blade surfaces (Madara & Selvan 2017).

3 MATERIALS AND METHOD

For this research purpose, three different types of products were manufactured through extrusion process. Firstly, multilayer hollow deck made of composite industries manufacturing waste and secondly solid composite panels. Lastly, different hollow bars were produced by different wind turbine blade (WTB) composition.

Once all the products were manufactured, they were left for about 40 day in a factory before taking them for testing. In addition, commercially available similar products (panel and deck) were bought from a local store (Stark, Joensuu) which were later compared. Following raw materials were used to produce above mentioned products.

3.1 FRP waste base

3.1.1 Scrap wind turbine blades (WTB)

Turbine blades are formed through a mixture of fiber reinforced plastics, resin matrix and other supporting materials like wood, foam and metals. Fibers in most of the blades are made with low cost glass fibers which consists of two-third of total weight in the blade (Mamanpush et al. 2018). Demolished turbine blades are shown in figure 18.

Figure 18. Scrap blades and their grinded form (Kallio 2018).

For this study, scrap blades were sent from a company called Virol from the Netherlands who are working in recycling sector (Virol, 2018). The decommissioned blades were first grinded

into smaller pieces (from dust size to 10 cm) and were shipped to the Conenor Ltd, Finland. It should be noted that only metals were removed using a magnetic separator from the WTB crushes and no other material fractions contained by demolished EOL blades. Thus, WTB materials used in this study includes materials like polyurethane, PVC and other foreign particles which are considered to be contaminants in pure GFRP waste from manufacturing.

The turbine waste composites were still a bit too large in sizes for direct processing than much better-looking Exel Composite's waste manufacturing fine particle waste in shavings.

3.1.2 Composite manufacturing waste

Exel Composites Oyj produces various composite products such as tubes, profiles and laminates for residential, commercial and industrial application (Exel 2018). It is understood that about 500 tons of wastes are being produced every year in Finnish production plants of Exel which are mainly landfilled due to lack of feasible handling mechanism. In this study, continuous lamination manufacturing waste from Exel's Mäntyharju plant, Finland were taken to the Conenor Ltd as shown in figure 19.

Figure 19. Two different types of Exel Composite's manufacturing waste (in agglomerated mixtures for extrusion) at Conenor Ltd.

Exel Composite's two different manufacturing wastes were used to produce multilayer decking board where inside core was filled with white Exel shavings and outside surface with Exel grey fine powder containing some carbon fibers. The reasons of varied colors are due to

the materials composition in waste stream such as carbon fibers and paper coating materials had an impact in the formation of black powders whereas grey colored waste was due to glass fibers and materials from grinding media (Koskinen 2018).

3.2 Wood pellets

Wood pellets are common material for heating in Finland due to their ecological and environmental benefits. Versowood (2017) is one of the companies producing such solid biofuels by using spruce and pine trees as shown in figure 20. Those pellets have diameter of 8 ± 1 mm, length smaller than 40 mm and energy density 16.9 MJ/kg. The wood species in such pellets are European red pine (Scots pine or *Pinus sylvestris*) and European white spruce (Norway spruce or *Picea abies*).

Figure 20. Wood pellets from Versowood.

The reason to select this specific type of wood source is because of its less moisture content, easy availability and cost. These pellets were used in all the formulations in this study.

3.3 Plastics

Polyethylene is commonly used thermoplastics material in wood plastic products. Conenor Ltd. had a few options available either in recycled and or in a virgin form such as recycled HDPE (also known as HDPEr or rHDPE), HDPE virgin, PEr, HDPE bio and recycled polypropylene

(PPr). Those different plastics were obtained from different companies such as Swerec (Sweden) as shown in figure 21.

Figure 21. Mixed colored PEr flakes (left) from Swerec, Uponor multilayer barrier pipe grade HDPEr (middle) and its crushes.

Recycled polyethylene (PEr) flakes (originating from consumer bottles) was obtained from Swerec, Sweden, whereas recycled HDPEr with blue barrier coating was obtained from Uponor pipes. Bio - HDPE, which consists of more than 94% biopolymers, was obtained from a company Braskem. In this study, bio - HDPE was used in reference products and rHDPE in decking whereas, PEr was used along with wind turbine blade waste.

3.4 Additives

Performance of WPCs can be improved by the addition of additives for instance; they provide antiaging property to the product. They are also helpful in preventing fading of wood flour and HDPE composites but doing so can increase the cost of production. Recently, inorganic fillers are being frequently used in WPC industries which is because of its UV absorbance property (Nguyen et al. 2018). Additives not only improve the quality of a product, but also ease extrusion functioning such as by the help of lubricants. Moreover, coupling agent helps to create a strong bonding between filler and matrix. Some of commonly used additives in WPCs are such as lubricants, wax, flame retardants, light stabilizer, coupling agent, coloring and blowing agents (Clariant 2009). Some of them were used in this study; listed in table 5.

Table 5. Additives used in the PE-based formulations

Processing aid	Coupling agent	Compatibilizer	Coloring
Lubricant Struktol® TPW 113	Licocene® PE MA 4351 fine grain	Recycloblend® 660	Red colored plastics granules

The Conenor Ltd. was able to provide all the additives including color pigments, compatibilizers and coupling agents needed for extrusion processing. At the end, it was kept the same additives for all the production process.

3.5 Process of agglomeration

The unique patent pending process of agglomeration is used by Conenor where a special type of highly intensive machine is used to mix the raw materials. The figure 22 shows a process of preparing raw material for extrusion for wind turbine blade (WTB) waste.

Figure 22. Demolished turbine blades from Virol (Netherlands) and agglomeration at Conenor Ltd.

As shown in figure, there were some moisture contents in downsized blades and therefore they were preheated before feeding them into high- intensity mixture for agglomeration. Meanwhile, recycled polyethylene (PEr) flakes and wood pellets were processed in high intensity mixture before mixing them with heated blade composites.

3.6 Material formulations and products manufacturing

In this study, 7 formulations and 8 products were manufactured through extrusion process. Three formulations were made to produce reference products which were meant to be compared with commercially available similar products whereas rest of the other products were produced to test the concentration effect of WTB content in hollow bars manufacturing. The following formulations as attached in tables 6–7 were prepared a day before the production.

Table 6. Evaluating materials effect in a single layer 60 mm x 40 mm x 8 mm hollow bars formulation

Recipes	Materials	Percentage content (%)
1. Ref A (WPC)	- Turbine blade (WTB)	0
	- PEr (Swerec)	30
	- Wood pellets	60
	- Processing aid	5
	- Compatibilizer	2
	- Coupling agent	3
2. Ref B	- Exel's shavings	30
	- PEr (Swerec)	30
	- Wood pellets	31
	- Processing aid	4
	- Compatibilizer	2
	- Coupling agent	3
3. Ref C	- WTB	30
	- Bio HDPE	30
	- Wood pellets	31
	- Processing aid	4
	- Compatibilizer	2
	- Coupling agent	3
4. 15%	- WTB	15
	- PEr (Swerec)	30
	- Wood pellets	46
	- Processing aid	4
	- Compatibilizer	2
	- Coupling agent	3
5. 30%	- WTB	30
	- PEr (Swerec)	30
	- Wood pellets	31
	- Processing aid	4
	- Compatibilizer	2
	- Coupling agent	3
6. 45%	- WTB	45
	- PEr (Swerec)	30
	- Wood pellets	16
	- Processing aid	4
	- Compatibilizer	2
	- Coupling agent	3

Table 7. Formulations for solid panel and multilayer hollow deck (for product test)

Recipes	Materials	Percentage content (%)
Solid Panel 395 mm x 10 mm	- WTB	30
	- Bio HDPE Virgin	30
	- Wood pellets	31
	- Processing aid	4
	- Compatibilizer	2
	- Coupling agent	3
Hollow decking board multilayer 140 mm x 28 mm	- Exel shavings	-> Core 30
	- Uponor HDPEr	30
	- Wood pellets	31
	- Processing aid	4
	- Compatibilizer	2
	- Coupling agent	3
Inside core shavings and outside grey powder	- Exel grey powder	-> Surface 35
	- Uponor HDPEr	30
	- Wood pellets	26
	- Processing aid	4
	- Compatibilizer	2
	- Coupling agent	3

Based on the formulations mentioned above, production of hollow bars, panel and the multilayer decks were manufactured. All the parameters were recorded by Conenor's extrusion machines and following products were manufactured as shown in images 23–25.

In the given images below, figure 23 shows the production parameters and Conenor's CONEX® CWE 380-1 extrusion which was used to manufacture hollow bars for material testing. In addition, Company's CONEX® CE 280-2 in figure 24 was used to produce WTB based solid panel. Figure 25-26 is an advanced extrusion machine CONEX® CWE 500-2 which was used to manufacture multilayer hollow decks.

Figure 23. Extrusion machine CONEX® CWE 380-1, hollow bar and different parameters used for Ref A, WTB 15% and Ref B hollow bars.

Figure 24. Panel production at CONEX® CE 280-2, extrusion parameters and a final product.

IN A_B_A-STRUCTURE WITH TWO ROTOR CONEX®

Figure 25-26. Conenor patented extrusion machine CONEX® CW500-2 which can produce multilayer profiles e.g. (back and front view from left to right), decking sample and the parameter used.

From all the above-mentioned extrusion processes, there were 8 different products manufactured which were then sent to University lab, Joensuu for further testing.

3.6.1 Commercial products for comparison

The commercial decking and panels were purchased from a local store called Stark (Stark-Suomi 2019), Joensuu which were also transported for tests to the university lab. UPM composite deck was purchased to compare with the Conenor decking, whereas Metsä Wood

Spruce Flex was bought to compare with the Conenor panels. Technical details of commercial products are shortly listed in table 8, although detailed specifications are attached in appendix 5–8.

Table 8. Technical descriptions of UPM deck and Metsä panel (UPM 2019, MetsäWood 2018)

Products	Features
<p data-bbox="212 969 762 996">UPM ProFi Deck 28 mm x 150 mm x 4000 mm</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Composite deck made of surplus by-product of self-adhesive label manufacturing processing - Lignin free, no greying - Clean polypropylene is used - No harmful chemicals in its composition - High resistance to moisture - Disposable as normal household waste - Brinell hardness (EN 1534): 28 N/mm² - MOR (EN 310): 13 N/mm² - Water absorption for 24 hr (EN 317): <2.5%.
<p data-bbox="217 1503 759 1563">Metsä Wood Spruce Flex 9 mm x 1200 mm x 2400 mm</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Nominal thickness 9mm and number of plies 3. - Coniferous plywood panel overlaid with UV resistant thermoplastic overlay - Overlay is bonded with plywood with a water-resistant glue. - Weather and boil-proof bonding - Resistant to most chemicals, crack, wear and impact. Moisture resistant - Application: ceiling, interior walls, packaging, agricultural construction. - MOR and E_{mod} 22.9 N/mm² and 9178 N/mm² in parallel testing () but 3.0 N/mm² and 422 N/mm² in perpendicular (⊥) testing, where standard EN 789 and EN 1058 used.

3.7 Mechanical testing and parameters

All the samples were kept in normal condition for a month soon after the production. Further, samples were again kept in a weather chamber of the university lab until the experiment day in Joensuu. The tests were divided into following categories:

- I. Hardness test: To test hardness of the materials (Brinell hardness) where standard SFS-EN 1534 was used (Standardisoimisliitto 2011).
- II. 3-point bending test or flexural test: To test the modulus of elasticity and rupture where standard EN ISO 178:2003 was followed (CEN 2003).
- III. Water immersion test: short-term (24 hour) and long-term (28 day) to observe the effects in mechanical properties.

In the beginning, samples were cut into pieces for 3-point bending test based on European standard given in table 9 (CEN 2003). The span was calculated through the following equation:

$$L = (16 \pm 1) \bar{h} \quad (1)$$

where, L represents span length and \bar{h} is average thickness of the specimen.

Table 9. Values of specimen width (b) in relation to thickness (h) (CEN 2003)

Dimensions in millimetres

Nominal thickness h	Width b^a
$1 < h \leq 3$	$25,0 \pm 0,5$
$3 < h \leq 5$	$10,0 \pm 0,5$
$5 < h \leq 10$	$15,0 \pm 0,5$
$10 < h \leq 20$	$20,0 \pm 0,5$
$20 < h \leq 35$	$35,0 \pm 0,5$
$35 < h \leq 50$	$50,0 \pm 0,5$
^a For materials with very coarse fillers, the minimum width shall be 30 mm.	

Based on table 9 standard, flexural test samples were prepared where thickness of the sample products was 10 mm average. Therefore, span of the cut samples was fixed at 160 mm for both panels and WTB hollow bars as well as the commercial panel because of their similar thickness. The deck material however had higher thickness (28 mm) and therefore span was calculated 448 mm.

Zwick equipment for mechanical testing had an issue to calculate modulus of rupture (MOR) and therefore it was done manually. This was calculated based on three-point bending test

for rectangular test pieces therefore MOR values for hollow bars and decking are not the same as solid structures:

$$\text{MOR} = \frac{3 \times F \times L}{2 \times b \times d^2} \quad (2)$$

where, F: Force applied, L: Span length, b: breadth and d: depth or thickness of the samples (Bishop 1999, CEN 2003).

For hardness testing, samples were cut into smaller pieces as shown in figure 27. In general, force is applied through the metallic ball (with known diameter) to the surface of the test samples in Brinell hardness. For this research, Zwick test machine was used and the standard SFS-EN 1534 was followed. According to this standard, maximum of 1000 N force was applied for 25 seconds before withdrawing the applied force.

Figure 27. Hardness test (A), 3-point bending test (B) and Zwick test machine set up (C) in LUKE's lab Joensuu.

Once the hardness tests were completed, Brinell hardness number (BHN) was calculated based on the depth made by steel ball and other parameters. To calculate BHN, following calculation was done based on SFS-EN 1534 standard (standardisoimisliitto 2011):

According to Pythagoras theorem,

$$H^2 = B^2 + P^2$$

$$5^2 = \left(\frac{d}{2}\right)^2 + (5 - h)^2$$

$$25 = \left(\frac{d^2}{4}\right) + (5 - h)^2$$

$$d = \sqrt{40 \times h - 4 \times h^2} \quad (3)$$

where,

D: Diameter of indenter (10 mm) or ball

d: diameter of indentation

H: Hypotenuse (OB in figure) or radius of the ball (D/2)

P: Perpendicular (OC in figure) = $(D \div 2) - h$

B: Base (BC in figure) = $d/2$

h: thickness or depth made by steel ball

Additionally, it was also found that Leyi et. al (2011) has also calculated 'd' in a similar way;

$$d = 2\sqrt{\left(\frac{D}{2}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{D}{2} - h\right)^2}$$

Then, Brinell hardness number was calculated by using following equation;

$$HB = \frac{2F}{g \times \pi \times D \times [D - \sqrt{D^2 - d^2}]} \quad (4)$$

where,

F is the maximum load applied force, $F = 1000 \text{ N}$;

g is the acceleration of gravity, $g = 9.8 \text{ m/s}^2$;

π (Pi) is a mathematical constant, $\pi = 3.1415$;

D is the diameter of the indenter, $D = 10 \text{ mm}$;

d: diameter of residual indentation

HB is the Brinell hardness (kgf/mm²); but in general, unit is not written as BHN is common method to indicate Brinell hardness number.

From all the test pieces, average value was taken from 5 different replicate samples. Then, based on average, standard deviation was calculated. In some cases, for instance panels, sample tests were high.

3.8 Water soaking (immersion test)

The first set of samples were cut based on the standard and two tests; Brinell hardness and flexural tests were carried in dry (normal) condition. Then, another set of specimens were poured into water to investigate the amount of water or moisture absorption as well as to compare their result before and after water immersion.

This 24 hour soaking test is considered as a short- term soaking. To begin this, about 40 cm long sample panels and hollow bars (100 cm) were measured their weight before and after pouring them into/from water. Calculation for water absorption (%) was determined according to the standard (Kärki & Martikka 2019):

$$\text{Water absorption (\%)} = \frac{\text{Specimen (after)} - \text{Specimen (before)}}{\text{Specimen (before)}} \times 100 \quad (5)$$

The precise dimension of decking samples was half meter long (500 mm × 140 mm × 28 mm), one meter long hollow bars (60 mm × 40 mm × 8 mm) and panels (395 mm × 40 mm × 10 mm). In addition, sample name WTB refers to wind turbine blades, REF to reference product, deck to hollow composite decking board. The samples were left in the university's laboratory sink as shown in figure 28.

Figure 28. Samples were left in water for 24 hour and 28 day immersion in university's laboratory sink.

For a long-term soaking test, similar sized panels (both commercial and Conenor) and hollow bars were taken into the sink full of water. For commercial panels, a piece was cut from large panel which was then measured before pouring into water for 28 day. Similar process was done in Conenor sample, but sample little larger compared to commercial panel. After 28 day immersion, they were measured again before cutting into several pieces for the tests. Similar process was done in 24 hour immersion.

For both commercial and Conenor deck products, 1 meter samples were cut into half (50 cm), measured the weights and poured them into water for 28 day. For both products, there were 4 deck samples for the test. After 28 day soaking, weights were measured again, and mechanical tests were done without any further cut.

For hollow bars, 1 meter samples of each hollow bars were weighed and poured into water for 24 hour and 28 day soaking. Weights were measured again after short- and long-term soaking. In this case, hollow bars were cut further into appropriate sizes according to the standard (in table 9) for mechanical tests.

4 RESULTS

There were primarily two tests done in this research, 3-point bending and Brinell hardness. Hollow bar's results were exclusively meant for materials testing in order to compare different variations in WTB samples to their reference products. Panel and deck products were tested and compared to their similar typed products available locally.

For hollow bars and decking test, all the result data are solely based on these types of structures as shown in figure 29, which cannot be equal or similar to that of solid structures. Hence, it is not recommended to compare these values to that of solid structures. In addition, since there were three different extrusion set-ups, which might produce different results even if the formulations are same and therefore one may not compare the result from one extrusion line to another.

Figure 29. Material types used in this research (From left to right: hollow bar for material testing, hollow decking, solid panel from Conenor and Metsä).

4.1 Water absorption

Weight of the different sample types were measured before pouring them into water for either 24 hour or 28 day. Moisture was not measured for any samples in dry or room temperature condition, thus 0% was assumed in order to analyze the moisture absorption by 24 hour and 28 day immersion tests. The size of samples was varied: hollow bars 1 m, decking 50 cm long and panels were 30–40 cm long in sizes. Figure 30 represents the percentage of water absorption by hollow bar samples and their reference products over the time of soaking trial.

Figure 30. Water absorption (%) by hollow bar samples after different soaking periods.

It was observed that water absorption by hollow bar ref A was highest among the bar samples. Least moisture was absorbed by WTB 45% hollow bar, which indicates that higher WTB contents are more likely to be better water resistant.

In panel products, huge difference between Conenor composite panels and Metsä Wood Spruce Flex panel was observed as shown in figure 31, where Conenor panels (0.07% to 0.41%) show practically no water absorption in any test.

Figure 31. Water absorption (%) by panels after different soaking periods.

Similarly, in decking material comparison, Conenor deck featured by far better characteristics over UPM ProFi when immersed in water for 28 days. It was observed 4.0% weight increment in UPM ProFi deck but only 3.4% in Conenor deck after 28 day immersion as shown in appendix 1.

4.2 Flexural (3-point bending) test

In this study, bending test was carried to test the material's modulus of elasticity (MOE or E_{mod}) and modulus of rupture (MOR) from different number of parallel samples for instance, 6 samples for bars and 4 samples for deck. Results are presented in bars where each bar represents the mean values and \pm standard deviation of the mean.

4.2.1 Result of modulus of elasticity (E_{mod})

In general, modulus of elasticity (MOE) varied between hollow and solid structures. Therefore, result below (figure 32) are not meant to be compared with any solid bars but only to the hollow bar samples of this specific sample types.

Figure 32. Mean values of modulus of elasticity (GPa) of hollow bars (reference bars A, B, C and bars with wind turbine blade composition 15%, 30%, 45% from left to right) in dry and after different soaking periods.

Values of E_{mod} in hollow bar samples achieved were acceptable in all the different samples except in Ref C (composition: 30% bio HDPE, WTB 30%, wood pellets 31%) where the moduli were increasing comparing normal condition to 24 hour and 28 day water immersion. Moreover, Ref A and Ref B have shown a clear effect of water immersion, thereby showing a trend of decreased E_{mod} from normal condition to 24 hour and 28 day immersion. Overall, hollow bar with 30% turbine blade material possessed the highest E_{mod} value among all although only difference between WTB 30 and ref C bar was PEr in WTB 30 instead of bio HDPE.

Statistically, most of the bar samples were not significant except WTB 45 where p-value was less than 0.05 between the groups as determined by one -way ANOVA. This shows that water immersion had effect on WTB 45% only. In addition, Ref B was close to being statistically significant (0.052), but other samples were not statistically significant as shown in appendix 2.

Since E_{mod} are generally calculated in solid structures such as bars or decks, above mentioned values cannot be compared to the corresponding solid structures. Moreover, panel tests have shown (figure 33) that modulus of elasticity in Metsä plywood has decreased significantly

from dry condition to 28 day soaking in contrast to Conenor's less changes. It has also shown that E_{mod} of hollow deck boards from Conenor deck was observed better than commercial UPM deck in normal (dry) and wet condition.

Figure 33. Mean values of modulus of elasticity (GPa) of panels (left) and deck (right) samples in dry and after different soaking periods.

In one-way ANOVA test, statistical significance was achieved 100% in Metsä spruce plywood samples, whereas Conenor samples didn't show significant differences between the groups as Conenor panels were not affected by water soaking. Further, decking from both commercial and Conenor products have shown a great statistical significance between the groups of different wetting trials as mentioned in table 10. Therefore, E_{mod} of both Conenor and UPM products has been significantly decreased after 28 day immersion.

Table 10. One-way ANOVA test for E_{mod} results in panel and deck samples

		ANOVA				
Panel		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Conenor	Between Groups	,562	2	,281	2,099	,162
	Within Groups	1,739	13	,134		
	Total	2,301	15			
Metsä	Between Groups	35,558	2	17,779	46,293	,000
	Within Groups	4,993	13	,384		
	Total	40,550	15			
Decking Conenor	Between Groups	,747	1	,747	11,228	,015
	Within Groups	,399	6	,066		
	Total	1,146	7			
UPM ProFi	Between Groups	,474	1	,474	1412,166	,000
	Within Groups	,002	6	,000		
	Total	,476	7			

4.2.2 Result of modulus of rupture (MOR)

MOR was calculated manually once Zwick test was performed. Figure 34 shows the MOR values in the form of bars where each bar represents the mean values and \pm standard deviation of the mean. In every case, independent variable is time which is being controlled.

Figure 34. Mean values of modulus of rupture (MPa) of hollow bars (reference bars A, B, C and bars with wind turbine blade composition 15%, 30%, 45% from left to right) in dry and after different soaking periods.

Interestingly, MOR of WTB 30 has shown highest number among the hollow bars in all condition with highest standard deviation whereas most contradictory result shown by Ref C. If considered the outlier in WTB 30 replicates, the optimal level of WTB-waste in WPC material formulations is likely around 30% and increasing concentration of WTB 45 do not enhance the mechanical performance. Even if outlier is avoided, results performed in between the WTB 15 and WTB 45. Overall, bars with WTB composition showed 2–3 MPa higher MOR and 0.5–1.5 GPa E_{mod} over reference bar products. In one- way ANOVA test as shown in appendix 3, have shown that water soaking did not affect significantly to any hollow bar samples. This indicates the hollow bar's applicability to outdoor application.

For panel products, MOR value of commercial panel was achieved 55.7 MPa to that of composite's 40.2 MPa in normal or dry condition as shown in figure 35. However, value has

weakened rapidly in Metsä panel but not to the Conenor panel over 24 hour and 28 day water immersion.

Figure 35. Mean value of modulus of rupture (MPa) comparison between Conenor panel - Metsä panel and Conenor hollow decking- UPM decking bars in dry and after different soaking periods.

In addition, when compared Conenor deck to commercial deck, result has proven that Conenor's waste-based deck has higher MOR values than UPM ProFi deck in both dry and immersion condition.

Result of one- way ANOVA test as shown in table 11, both Conenor and Metsä panel samples were statistically significant between the groups as there was clear effect of water treatment in their MOR properties. But when analyzed deck products, 28 day immersion had affected MOR values significantly only to UPM decking ($p= 0.000$) but not the Conenor's decking ($p= 0.124$). This indicates panel product from Conenor is useful in outdoor structural application.

Table 11. One- way ANOVA test for MOR result in panel and deck products

Panel		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Conenor	Between Groups	171,588	2	85,794	5,174	,024
	Within Groups	198,994	12	16,583		
	Total	370,582	14			
Metsä	Between Groups	1934,916	2	967,458	21,850	,000
	Within Groups	531,317	12	44,276		
	Total	2466,233	14			
Deck						
Conenor	Between Groups	8,282	1	8,282	3,196	,124
	Within Groups	15,548	6	2,591		
	Total	23,831	7			
UPM ProFi	Between Groups	8,385	1	8,385	409,750	,000
	Within Groups	,123	6	,020		
	Total	8,507	7			

4.3 Brinell hardness test result

Brinell hardness was calculated as BHN number (kgF/mm^2) which is also a common method to represent material's hardness. Each bars represents the mean value of BHN with \pm standard deviation of the mean as shown in figure 36.

Figure 36. Mean BHN values of hollow bars in dry and after different soaking periods.

This result has shown a big fluctuation in BHN numbers especially 24 hour immersion condition. Only, bar WTB 30 has shown the right pathway where hardness in dry condition has higher value to that of lower values in 24 hour and 28 day immersion. Among all the hollow bars, Ref B has shown highest number of BHN value (3.68). Reasons for such variability can be seen in analysis down below in further discussion.

Statistical analysis, ANOVA test has also proven the fact that WTB 30 hollow bar is statistically most significant between the groups ($p= 0.017$). Further, Ref B ($p= 0.020$) and WTB 45 ($p= 0.033$) hollow bars were found to be significant between the groups whereas other three hollow bars were not significant. This indicates that treatments had effect on hardness properties of WTB 30, ref B and WTB 45 bars. Additionally, this can also be seen in figure 36 that mean BHN are decreased from dry condition to immersion condition only to those

samples which were statistically significant. The detail result data and statistical tests are also attached in appendix 4.

Hardness values in between Conenor composite panels and Metsä plywood panels were hugely different. Result has clearly shown in figure 37 that plywood panel was too soft to compare with Conenor based composite panel. It was observed that Conenor panels were 5–6 times harder than those of commercial panels in all condition. In addition, it has also found that BHN of waste based Conenor deck are higher than commercial decking in both dry condition and after immersion.

Figure 37. Mean Brinell hardness comparison between Conenor panel to Metsä panel (left) and Conenor hollow decks to UPM decks (right) in both dry and after different soaking periods.

Furthermore, one-way ANOVA (table 12) has shown that statistical significance in Conenor's panels as hardness properties were affected by water immersions. This can also be seen in figure 37 where BHN are decreased from dry condition to 24-hour and 28-day immersion condition.

Table 12. One-way ANOVA test for hardness result in panels and deck products

Panel		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Conenor	Between Groups	2,532	2	1,266	6,637	,017
	Within Groups	1,717	9	,191		
	Total	4,249	11			
Metsä Plywood	Between Groups	,220	2	,110	2,724	,119
	Within Groups	,363	9	,040		
	Total	,582	11			
Deck						
Conenor	Between Groups	,361	1	,361	,943	,338
	Within Groups	14,544	38	,383		
	Total	14,905	39			
UPM ProFi	Between Groups	6,370	1	6,370	152,295	,000
	Within Groups	1,589	38	,042		
	Total	7,959	39			

In contrast, Metsä Wood Spruce Flex practically absorbed higher moisture contents upon 24 hour and 28 day immersion (figure 31). However, statistical result was not efficient due to the same Brinell hardness test condition for both Conenor's composite panel and Metsä panel. On the other hand, difference of BHN in commercial deck from UPM was found to be statistically significant between the groups. This indicates that treatments had affected the hardness properties in UPM deck but not to the Conenor's deck.

5 DISCUSSION

5.1 Validity and reliability of result

Mechanical properties of wood plastic composites were tested in hollow bars, panels and deck products. For materials test, demolished wind turbine blades were altered 15%, 30% and 45% in wood plastic hollow bars to investigate better composition which was then compared to their reference bars. For product to product test, Conenor's waste based composite panels and decks were tested against locally available Metsä Wood Spruce Flex panels and UPM ProFi decks respectively.

To achieve the objectives of WTB waste performance in WPC composition, tests were carried out in normal or room temperature condition and after water immersion for 24 hour and 28 days in order to evaluate the properties before and after soaking. Overall, hollow bar specimens absorbed water 0.39% (least) to 2.85% (highest) during 28 day trials. Further, composite panels were observed almost completely water resistance even after 28 days of immersion in contrast to Metsä Wood Spruce Flex's incomparable absorption rate. Furthermore, Conenor's composite decks absorbed only 3.4% moisture in contrast to UPM ProFi deck's 4.0% absorption after 28 day soaking.

Mechanically, average modulus of elasticity of Metsä panel (6.8 GPa) was higher than Conenor's composite panels (4.2 GPa) in dry condition but E_{mod} values were significantly affected by water treatments in Metsä panel as the E_{mod} reached 3.8 GPa in contrast to Conenor's 4.5 GPa after 28 day immersion. Similar trend was also achieved in modulus of rupture where Metsä panel's 55.7 MPa dropped to 22.9 MPa from dry condition to after 28 day immersion in contrast to 40.2 MPa to 35.01 MPa in Conenor's panel. Therefore, Conenor's panel possessed better mechanical properties over commercial panel from Metsä. In addition, deck to deck comparison showed Conenor's deck showed superior mechanical properties over UPM ProFi deck where E_{mod} of Conenor deck is 2.23 GPa in dry condition, 1.6 GPa after 28 day immersion in contrast to UPM's 1.45 GPa (dry) and 0.97 GPa after 28 day immersion. Similar trend was observed in flexural strength property where MOR of Conenor's deck was 16.93 MPa and UPM's 15.58 MPa in dry condition but dropped to 14.89 MPa and 13.53 MPa after 28 day immersion respectively.

To increase the reliability of results, several replicate samples were tested. In addition, initial trials were done a month prior to the final experiments to see if the laboratory testing machine would be suitable to test selected composite products. Result varied initially when the width of deck products was longer than the supporting metallic base. Later, issue was fixed and then work was resumed followed by composite standards. Despite fixing the issue, some of the results such as hollow bars ref A and WTB 15 did not show practically acceptable performance where hardness values were higher even after 28 day immersion which is believed to be affected by possible errors in laboratory processing while sample preparation and testing.

However, accuracy of results could have been improved if there would have been more replicates. Especially in commercial deck, sample numbers were rather low (4 replicates) for various reasons and hence this affected to the statistical variance of results. Further, commercial panel (1.05 BHN) was extremely soft in comparison to Conenor panel (6.9 BHN), which showed differences in mechanical properties due to high moisture absorption by Metsä panel (66% after 28 day immersion) compared to 0.41% by Conenor panel. Nevertheless, considering various sample types (bars, decks and panels) and their testing, research may well go beyond this thesis if needed to analyse particular type of product. Therefore, analysis for this study is focused entirely based on those results obtained within the given material parameters.

5.2 Effect of water immersion

Mechanical properties of WPCs often degrade by water absorption, which usually comes with increasing amount of natural fiber content in their composition. It is believed wood is highly used fiber material in WPC which has an influence over water absorption (Kärki & Martikka 2019). However, researchers have figured out a way to minimize moisture resistance in WPC by increasing the amount of compatibilizer. This can also be improved by the addition of another additive coupling agent, which reduces moisture absorption and swelling thus boosting durability and dimensional stability (Hyvärinen et al. 2019, Adhikary et al. 2008). Licocene® PE MA coupling agent from Clariant (2009) used in all the Conenor products is believed to be assisted for better edge quality, thereby helping against the water absorption.

Among all the hollow bar, Ref A bar showed the largest variation where only 0.35% of water was absorbed after 24 hour immersion which was then increased to 2.85% during the 28 day

soaking. Ref A is also a pure WPC with 0% WTB but wood pellets (60%), PE (30%) and remaining additives. As mentioned earlier, it is clear that high wood content in Ref A may have led to the higher water uptake level (2.85% after 28 day immersion). Further, less water absorption was achieved in bar WTB 45 (0.39% after 28 day immersion), where the content of wood pellets (16%) was the least among all samples. Moreover, bar WTB 15% contained 46% of wood (second highest after ref A) and therefore the second biggest variation was noticed (1.63% moisture absorption after 28 day immersion).

In this study, baseline product for composite panel comparison was chosen as Metsä Wood Spruce Flex panel, which showed a clear difference in amount of water absorption compared to Conenor's composite panel. Metsä panel generally contains 7–9% of moisture after leaving the mill but changes depending upon the surrounding conditions (Metsä 2018). Therefore, those panels were dried in a constant temperature condition in lab before soaking them into water. Yet, during the 24 hour immersion test gave 26.2% of moisture absorption in contrast to the Conenor panel's 0.07%. Further, 28 day soaking could not affect much to the composite panels (0.4%) but to the commercial panel, the influence was significantly higher (66.3%). Therefore, manual leaflet from producer has clearly suggested to have 1 mm/m expansion gap in fastened panels for moisture movement whereas minimum of 10 mm expansion gap should be left in between floor panelling and adjoining structures (Metsä 2018). In this study, swelling of the samples due to water absorption was not measured.

Deck to deck product comparisons, however, were more similar than that of panel products in terms of appearance and properties. For 28 day immersion, Conenor deck (3.4%) possessed slightly better performance over UPM ProFi deck (4.0%) in terms of moisture absorption. In general, moisture absorption and mechanical properties of WPCs typically depends on the interaction between plastics matrix and fiber materials, where good interaction between them provides better mechanical properties (Hyvärinen et al. 2019). Less absorption in Conenor deck means there was a better interaction between plastics matrix HDPEr and fiber as Exel manufacturing waste. This could have also benefitted as a multilayer product where surface layer contained grey powder and core layer with black powder consisting carbon fibers and coating waste. Nonetheless, Conenor's multilayer deck with FRP waste has proven its performance throughout the tests.

5.3 Effect on flexural properties

Several studies have been done in the field of wood plastic composites, where recycled materials have been used as raw materials (Taufiq et al. 2018, Hyvärinen et al. 2019, Najafi 2013). In this study, flexural testing of all the specimens were measured using 3-point bending tests where European standard EN ISO 178:2003 was followed. The results were shown in computer screen by Zwick machine, except MOR values which was later calculated manually by using a formula as shown in equation (2) of page number 46. Following chapters will further analyse on modulus of rupture and modulus of elasticity.

5.3.1 Effect of wetting on composite's modulus of elasticity

Based on the performed 3-point bending tests, results were presented in figures 32–33. As can be observed, bar WTB 30 has shown a highest value (E_{mod}) among all bars in all wetting states. WTB 30, however, had an exceptional outlier which resulted in an overall value comparatively higher than any other hollow bars. When excluded an outlier, values of both E_{mod} and MOR resulted in between WTB 15 and WTB 45 in all condition, but still higher than reference products. The trend has clarified that bars with WTB composition show higher stiffness compared to their reference samples. Key issue while comparing the result between bar samples, Ref C has shown an unexpected trend, where modulus of elasticity is getting gradually higher in 28 day immersion ($E_{mod\ 28\ day} > E_{mod\ 24\ hr} > E_{mod\ dry\ condition}$).

When analyzing composition of specimen, the only difference between Ref C and WTB 30 was found in the applied plastics matrix: Ref C used Bio HDPE, in contrast to recycled PE in bar WTB 30 samples. Moreover, both Ref A and Ref B followed the pattern as expected ($E_{mod\ dry\ condition} > E_{mod\ 24\ hr} > E_{mod\ 28\ day}$), where average E_{mod} in bar ref B had slight advantage over ref A. This could be because of lower wood content in Ref B compared to the Ref A sample. In some cases, result did not seem highly promising in bar samples as expected such as Young's modulus in 24 hour immersion showed lower values than soaking after 28 days. These issues were discussed with experts in the field (Vilkkii 2019, Marttila 2019) and following concerns were raised:

- Fiber materials in WTB bars were not entirely pure as it was noticed (figure 16), some foreign particles such as aluminum, copper, brass and possible other unknown materials which could have impacted the outcome.

- Sample preparation involved techniques like smoothening the edges which may have axed the plastics surface from the edge.
- Since there were many sample pieces (each 1 m long) of same products extruded, result can be slightly different if the tested product was the first cut of the extrusion. In this type of specimen, foreign particles from earlier processed products from the same extruder might have fed the unwanted material to the bar samples.
- In some cases, large particle defect in materials composition could have affected.
- Migneault et al. (2009), discussed about the effect of fiber size and role of lubricant in water absorption thereby reducing the mechanical properties. In addition, processing condition, time, pressure, cooling rate and so on may have affected the flexural as well as hardness properties.

Results have shown that equal concentration of WTB, PEr (recycled PE) and wood pellets in composite formulation would result in better Young's modulus. But, statistical point of view showed clear significance only in WTB 45 samples. This doesn't mean there are no practical significance in other samples as the specimen sizes were relatively low (6 replicates) for each bar and that could have affected the statistical results.

On the other hand, commercial Metsä plywood panel had higher E_{mod} value than Conenor's panel in dry condition because of high wood content composition and laminate structure in Metsä panel. Even though Metsä's spruce flex panel is believed to be water resistant due to their transparent sealing paint in the edges (Metsä 2018), water may have been absorbed when cut and soaked them without using water repellent paint. In contrast, Conenor panel was made with wood plastics material. Hence, naturally this didn't exhibit much fluctuations after 24 hour and 28 day immersion and only absorbed small amount of water. This fact has also proven by one-way ANOVA test which showed plywood panel's cent percent significance after immersion. This clarifies that water treatment in Metsä panel had affected the modulus of elasticity.

Moreover, mean E_{mod} of Conenor deck was achieved higher than that of commercial deck where differences of 0.78 GPa and 0.65 GPa was observed in dry condition and after 28 day soaking respectively (figure 33). This indicates a strong possibility for composite industry, like Exel, who are producing composite manufacturing waste. It is also a positive sign for extrusion

industry, which can use additional raw materials from waste stream and still provide the better-quality products in terms of elastic modulus. It is also stressed that material composition in UPM ProFi deck used clean polypropylene (PP) (UPM 2019) as their plastics matrix whereas Conenor deck have used HDPEr from Uponor multilayer barrier pipes. In a separate study where WPC were manufactured through hot press molding, Adhikary et al. (2008) have noted that modulus of elasticity (MOE) were higher when HDPEr was used rather than virgin HDPE for same amount of wood. Statistically, one- way ANOVA has shown a clear indication of statistical significances in both type of decks despite having low number of deck samples (only 4).

5.3.2 Effect of wetting on composite's flexural strength (modulus of rupture)

Based on the performed 3-point bending tests, mean values of MOR results are presented in figures 34–35. MOR measures bond strength of the test sample which was calculated manually based on the given equation (equation 2). As presented in figure 34, hollow bar with WTB 30 exhibited better flexural strength among all bars. Further, pattern of bar chart is similar to that of modulus of elasticity where bar Ref C performed like an outlier. Again, this fluctuation could have been affected by earlier mentioned assumptions of the chapter 5.3.1. As shown, MOR value of 28.7 MPa was observed in bar WTB 30% sample in normal condition whereas lowest MOR (22.2 MPa) was observed in Ref A bar in same condition. Statistically, none of the differences were significant ($P > 0.05$) among any samples in dry or after immersion condition. This clarifies that water soaking did not have significant effect on MOR properties of bar samples. However, result could have been different if sample sizes were large.

In addition, panels from Metsä spruce plywood exhibited notable difference; average of 15.5 MPa higher flexural strength than Conenor's panel in normal condition. But composite panel remained much less affected by immersion in contrast to the Metsä plywood's drastic reduction due to water absorption. After 28 day soaking, Conenor panel exhibited average 12.1 MPa higher than flexural strength of Metsä panel. Statistically too, both kinds of panels showed statistically significant differences as the indication of water absorption in MOR properties. An example curve diagram of variations in maximum force used in reference panels in different conditions can be observed in figure 38.

Figure 38. Deformation curves of Metsä wood spruce flex replicate samples (ref-p1-dry, ref-p1-w24 and ref-p1-w28) in dry, after 24 hour and 28 day immersion condition.

This figure is a representative model of replicate samples of Metsä panels in different conditions, where average F_{max} of 229.9 N, 153.6 N and 99.9 N was observed while deforming those panels in dry, after 24 hour and after 28 day immersion condition. Trend in figure 38 has clarified that amount of forces needed to deform above-mentioned replicate specimens were comparatively higher in normal condition than after water soaking conditions.

Similarly, flexural strength of Conenor composite was observed to be 1.4 MPa higher than practically similar looking UPM ProFi deck after all soaking trials. An interesting fact was noticed from both samples: only about 2 MPa reduction in MOR value after 28 day immersion. High MOR values in Conenor's composites could be because of its HDPEr matrix and Exel composites manufacturing waste in its composition in contrast to the UPM's paper waste and clean PP. Conenor used in its composition wood pellets (Versowood 2017) made of Norway spruce and Scots pine in contrast to the UPM's lignin free surplus by- product from industry (UPM 2019). Spruce has generally longer fibers than pine, thus providing better mechanical properties (Heräjärvi 2018). Further, several researches have been conducted in fiber (wood)/plastic ratio for different processing technologies, such as extrusion and injection molding, where some study have found higher ratio would give better MOR especially in injection molding (Sommerhuber et al. 2016, Mordi 2014). Some have observed low flexural strength when increased wood content in extrusion (Chaudemanche et al. 2018).

5.4 Effect of wetting on composite's Brinell hardness

Hardness represents the resistance of a material to deformation such as scratching and surface penetration (Barajas et al. 2017). There are many test methods for hardness but

Brinell hardness was chosen in this research because of its availability and this also considered as authoritative measurement within scientific community due to its high precision (Leyi et al. 2011). Brinell hardness was performed by Zwick test machine, where standard SFS-EN 1534:2010 was followed. The hardness was represented as BHN (unit: kgf/mm²) and this was calculated by using equation 4 mentioned in page number 47.

Based on hollow bar results, most consistent BHN has shown by bar WTB 30, as this was similar case in E_{mod} and MOR results. Secondly, bar with ref B content exhibited the property of highest resistance to permanent deformation. Further, ref C content and bar WTB 45 did not express much difference even after immersion. However, remaining other hollow bar samples performed unexpectedly as hardness was higher in wet condition than in dry. Reasons for such alteration could have been originated from processing condition as well as other reasons mentioned in chapter 5.3.1 of page 63–64. Statistically, WTB 30 showed its highest significance between the groups followed by ref B and WTB 45 bars. Other half of the samples didn't show statistical significance. When analyzed through the bar's composition, bio HDPE in ref C may have impacted its hardness but for ref A (pure WPC) bar, BHN was higher after 28 day immersion than in a dry condition. In other samples such as bar WTB 30 and WTB 45, significant differences in hardness was observed despite absorbing less water during immersion. But hardness in ref B appears to be affected by Exel's manufacturing waste in its composition.

For panel comparison, composite panel from Conenor expectedly demonstrated higher BHN than Metsä Wood Spruce Flex because of differences in material composition as one was made with WPC, whereas other one was thermoplastic coated plywood. The variation in hardness of composite panel before and after immersion of 28 day was found at BHN 1.5 in contrast to the plywood panel's 0.2. However, results obtained for plywood do not represent the true hardness value of such product which is because of technical error during experimentation. For instance, Brinell hardness was applied in a same condition (e.g. force) for both Metsä Wood Spruce Flex and Conenor's composite panel. But in reality, Metsä panel was observed extremely soft as shown in figure 39 to be compared, thus resulting impractical values. However, there was still a clear indication of BHN differentiation within Metsä panel before and after soaking.

Figure 39. Brinell hardness failure test in Metsä wood spruce flex panel (left) and Conenor's composite panel at University lab in Joensuu.

In addition, despite having an enormous difference in water absorption after 24 hour and 28 day immersion in Metsä panel, statistical significant was not seen due to the processing error. It was learned that force could have been minimized in the case of Metsä Wood Spruce Flex Brinell harness testing. But composite panel showed statistically significant differences between the group (24 hour and 28 day immersion) although the number of samples were relatively low. Effect of water in composite Conenor's panel over different time periods can also be observed in result, where BHN of Conenor deck decreased from dry to 24 hour immersion and 28 day immersion by 6.9, 6.7 and 5.4 respectively. Unit of BHN is kgf/mm^2 but in practice just a BHN numbers is given.

On the other hand, Conenor's deck and UPM deck were similar in many ways such as size, appearance and processing method (extrusion). It is stressed that both deck products were hollow boards and obviously resulted BHN were not equal to that of solid deck. Calculations are not done in this thesis to find out BHN of solid structures of their respective hollow decking boards. Based on the result, the hardness value of waste based Conenor deck (3.4 BHN) remained better than similar product from UPM (BHN 3.0) in normal condition but BHN

was dropped to 2.3 in UPM sample in contrast to the Conenor's 3.2 BHN after 28 day immersion. This clarifies the better hardness in Conenor's deck compared to UPM ProFi deck in all condition.

In addition, it has not been ignored the datasheet from UPM which has mentioned hardness 28 N/mm² (2.86 BHN) of UPM ProFi deck based on EN 1534 standard (UPM 2019). Those minor differences to measure BHN values can be considered as processing error.

By materials composition, it is noted that UPM ProFi is made with lignin free materials and have used virgin polypropylene in contrast to the Conenor's HDPEr and composite manufacturing waste. Not only the plastics matrix may have affected the result but also multilayer design of Conenor deck may have had benefits over UPM ProFi deck. Interestingly, both products have a similarity in terms of disposal where waste from production processes and off- cuts can be recycled into new deck product manufacturing. This particular recycling was done by author several times during the sample preparation and formulation at Conenor Ltd. Therefore, disposal route of Conenor deck are much alike to that of commercial deck.

Many studies have been done in the field of Brinell hardness and stress-strain behavior, but recent researches are still focused on Brinell hardness measurement process to find the best suitable mechanism (Leyi et al. 2011, Kaymakci & Ayrimis 2014). Kaymakci & Ayrimis (2014) revealed the relationship between Brinell hardness and tensile properties. They used sawdust flour, polypropylene and coupling agent (with/without) to make WPCs. Result showed increasing sawdust would increase the Brinell hardness but lowered tensile properties. Therefore, sawdust flour between 30–40% along with coupling agent addition would improve both hardness and stress-strain property of WPCs. Furthermore, similar outcome was also observed by Homkhiew et al. (2015) in their experiment. However, their study was extended to investigate the effect of UV stabilizer. This suggested that the mechanical properties of WPCs such as hardness and strength were decreased by addition of UV stabilizers, but suggested addition of coupling agent brings economic benefits and better mechanical properties.

6 CONCLUSIONS

The aim of this graduation thesis was to analyze the effect of glass fiber reinforced plastics into wood plastics composites applications. This study included two rapidly growing industries where waste stream from one industry has been used to make raw material for another industry thus supporting the value of circular economy. Recently, WPCs industry has been skyrocketed especially in China and North America because of its high demand in many sectors such as construction. At the same time, wind energy has also gained popularity because of a global demand of sustainable energy. Turbine blade is one of the major components in wind energy system which is made of GFRP composite. Most of the parts in wind energy system can be recycled but blades recycling has been a concern due to legislation restricting landfilling of such products as well as thermoset composition of blades that cannot be re-melted ones heated. However, Conenor's expertise in the field of extrusion and the author's motivation to investigate the waste turbine blades into WPCs has been explored.

In this study, three different products were manufactured through Conenor's extrusion technology. Firstly, six pieces of WPC hollow bars with different composition of wind blades and reference products were manufactured in order to analyze the WTB effect. Second and third product types were composite panel (solid) and multilayer deck (hollow) which were later compared to their similar products purchased from local market. Further, flexural (E_{mod} and MOR) and Brinell hardness (BH) tests were done by Zwick testing machine in LUKE laboratory, Joensuu where appropriate standard was followed from the laboratory booklet. For all the specimens, experiments were carried out in three conditions; dry condition, after 24 hour immersion and 28 day immersion. After the result, statistical analysis was performed through one-way ANOVA test.

Water immersion result among all the bar samples have shown highest amount of water absorption by ref A because of higher wood content in contrast to WTB 45 sample which absorbed less moisture due to low the low wood content composition. Moreover, both panels and decks products comparison showed better performance of Conenor's products over commercial products thereby hinting practically no water absorption when soaked for 24 hour and 28 day. In addition, 3-point bending test among hollow bar samples has resulted

highest value of E_{mod} and MOR for WTB 30 bar in all condition (outlier included), hence proving the optimal level of WTB 30% but not more because higher concentration did not significantly enhance the mechanical performance although, higher concentration of WTB in bar (e.g. WTB 45) absorbed low water, thus maintaining the same level of mechanical performance before and after immersion for 28 day. Overall, WTB waste content at 30–45% in hollow bars showed greater performances, thus suggesting this composition for bar application.

The panel comparison showed that Metsä Wood Spruce Flex plywood panel exhibited 15.5 MPa higher flexural strength of Metsä panel than Conenor's panel in dry (normal) condition but strength was significantly reduced after 28 day immersion (Conenor panel's 12.1 MPa higher than Metsä panel). This is because of the higher wood content in Metsä Wood Spruce Flex panel composition. Result has been analyzed through ANOVA test which also showed higher significance in Metsä Wood Spruce Flex panel due to significant changes in their (E_{mod} and MOR) after moisture absorption. Moreover, decks comparison exhibited 1.4 MPa higher MOR and 0.6 GPa higher E_{mod} of Conenor's waste based hollow product than UPM ProFi commercial decking in dry condition. But, both MOR and E_{mod} were in similar range even after 28 day immersion. The similar result was observed in Brinell hardness test where both panel and deck from Conenor performed superior compared to their respective commercial products in all condition. When analyzed Brinell hardness in hollow bars, WTB 30 exhibited better result in all condition which was also proven significant by statistical analysis.

Despite having few limitations in laboratory processing and low sample volume, result was sufficient enough to suggest best possible materials composition for WPCs bar. Further, Exel's composite manufacturing waste in decking and WTB waste in panel products have shown greater performance to their respective similar commercial products, thus indicating their potential to replace such similar products. However, it is still recommended to use best possible pure WTB materials to get even better properties of such hollow bars and solid panels.

7 REFERENCES

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APPENDICES

Appendix 1. Mass values of hollow bars, panels and decks before and after soaking.

This presents all the mass measurements (in gram) before and after samples were soaked for 24 hour and 28 days immersion.

WATER ABSORPTION BY HOLLOW BARS, PANELS AND DECKS (Weight in grams)										
Result after 24 hour immersion test										
	BAR-REF A	BAR-REF B	BAR-REF C	BAR-WTB15	BAR-WTB30	BAR-WTB45	Conenor Panel	Conenor deck	Metsä panel	
Dry condition	1507,96	1609,43	1566,02	1546,44	1600,52	1618,13	1008,41	1464,26	197,41	
After 24 hr immersion	1513,29	1613,77	1570,09	1554,51	1605,24	1621,95	1009,14	1472,12	249,09	
% Increase	0,35	0,27	0,26	0,52	0,29	0,24	0,07	0,54	26,17	
Result after 28 day immersion										
	BAR-REF A	BAR-REF B	BAR-REF C	BAR-WTB15	BAR-WTB30	BAR-WTB45	Conenor Panel	Metsä panel	UPM ProFi Deck	Conenor deck
Dry condition	1509,83	1607,37	1579,57	1548,79	1595,57	1619,28	1000,3	366,25	1490,175	1390,466667
After 28 day immersion	1552,93	1622,51	1595,5	1573,96	1607,8	1625,58	1004,38	608,92	1549,805	1438,035
% Increase	2,85	0,94	1,01	1,63	0,77	0,39	0,41	66,26	4,00	3,42

Appendix 2. One-way ANOVA test in modulus of elasticity results of hollow bars

		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
RefA	Between Groups	1,437	2	,719	1,776	,203
	Within Groups	6,069	15	,405		
	Total	7,507	17			
Ref B	Between Groups	4,287	2	2,144	3,622	,052
	Within Groups	8,876	15	,592		
	Total	13,164	17			
Ref C	Between Groups	,397	2	,198	,512	,609
	Within Groups	5,813	15	,388		
	Total	6,210	17			
WTB 15	Between Groups	,995	2	,497	1,855	,191
	Within Groups	4,022	15	,268		
	Total	5,016	17			
WTB30	Between Groups	5,164	2	2,582	1,640	,227
	Within Groups	23,614	15	1,574		
	Total	28,778	17			
WTB45	Between Groups	3,369	2	1,685	3,846	,045
	Within Groups	6,570	15	,438		
	Total	9,939	17			

Appendix 3. One-way ANOVA test in modulus of rupture results of hollow bars

		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
RefA	Between Groups	7,320	2	3,660	,383	,688
	Within Groups	143,230	15	9,549		
	Total	150,550	17			
Ref B	Between Groups	33,470	2	16,735	3,100	,075
	Within Groups	80,967	15	5,398		
	Total	114,437	17			
Ref C	Between Groups	17,075	2	8,537	,965	,403
	Within Groups	132,722	15	8,848		
	Total	149,797	17			
WTB 15	Between Groups	18,904	2	9,452	1,257	,313
	Within Groups	112,770	15	7,518		
	Total	131,673	17			
WTB30	Between Groups	104,995	2	52,497	,915	,422
	Within Groups	860,323	15	57,355		
	Total	965,318	17			
WTB45	Between Groups	33,500	2	16,750	2,546	,112
	Within Groups	98,680	15	6,579		
	Total	132,179	17			

Appendix 4. One-way ANOVA test in Brinell hardness results of hollow bars

		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
RefA	Between Groups	1,385	2	,693	1,318	,304
	Within Groups	6,305	12	,525		
	Total	7,690	14			
Ref B	Between Groups	3,811	2	1,905	5,470	,020
	Within Groups	4,180	12	,348		
	Total	7,991	14			
Ref C	Between Groups	,007	2	,004	,005	,995
	Within Groups	9,059	12	,755		
	Total	9,067	14			
WTB 15	Between Groups	1,633	2	,816	2,958	,090
	Within Groups	3,312	12	,276		
	Total	4,945	14			
WTB30	Between Groups	3,521	2	1,760	5,839	,017
	Within Groups	3,618	12	,301		
	Total	7,138	14			
WTB45	Between Groups	1,766	2	,883	4,609	,033
	Within Groups	2,299	12	,192		
	Total	4,066	14			

Appendix 5. Metsä Wood Spruce Flex panel's technical datasheet

Spruce Ply

Flex

SURFACE PROPERTIES

The surface of the overlay is slightly structured to improve wear and scratch resistance. The overlay is elastic, tough and does not crack easily. The overlay is safe to use and free of chlorine, halogens, plasticizers, formaldehyde and heavy metals.

The surface is easy to clean with water and normal detergents. Strong acids, alkalis and e.g. acetone may cause visual changes on the surface.

Metsä Wood Spruce Flex has a ready-finished surface that is susceptible to scratches due to its softer appearance. Due to the structure of the coniferous veneers, some structures may be visible on the overlaid surface. Extra caution has to be taken in handling and storing the panels to prevent damage. Extreme moisture penetration may cause visible changes to the appearance of the product.

Technical properties of the surface

- Taber value is approx. 2000 R*
- Colour stability 6-7 according to DIN 54404
- Colour change $\Delta E < 1$ according to ISO 4892-2 (600 h)
- Crack resistance EN13696 no cracks
- Impact resistance Class IC3 according to EN438-2

* Abrasion resistance is tested according to EN 438-2 / DIN 53799

EDGE SEALING

Panel edges are sealed against moisture absorption with transparent edge sealing paint. Even though edge sealing hinders the absorption of moisture into the panel, it does not eliminate it completely.

PANEL SIZES

Metsä Wood Spruce Flex is available in sizes:

- 2400 / 2440 mm x 1200 / 1220 mm
- 2400 / 2440 mm x 600 / 610 mm

The first measurement indicates the orientation of the surface veneer grain.

SIZE TOLERANCES

Measured in accordance with standard EN 324, the plywood size and squareness tolerances meet the requirements of EN 315.

PANEL TOLERANCES

LENGTH / WIDTH	TOLERANCE
< 1000 mm	±1 mm
1000-2000 mm	±2 mm
> 2000 mm	±3 mm
Squareness	±0.1 % or ±1 mm/m
Edge straightness	±0.1 % or ±1 mm/m

THICKNESS, STRUCTURES AND THICKNESS TOLERANCES

THICKNESSES, STRUCTURES AND THICKNESS TOLERANCES OF THE PANELS*

NOMINAL THICKNESS (mm)	NUMBER OF PLYS (no.)	THICKNESS TOLERANCE		WEIGHT kg/m ²
		min. (mm)	max. (mm)	
9	3	7	9	4.1
12	4	10	12	5.5
15	5	13	15	6.9
18	6	16	18	8.3
21	7	19	21	9.7

* The moisture content of the product affects its dimensions

* Average density of Metsä Wood Spruce plywood is 460 kg/m³ (at a relative humidity of 65%)

* Special structures and thicknesses are available on request

* Customised tolerances are possible but must be agreed separately

BONDING CLASSES

Metsä Wood plywood panels are bonded with a weather- and boil-resistant phenol formaldehyde adhesive (WBP, BFU, AW, exterior).

The gluing meets the requirements of the following international standards:

- EN 314-2 / Class 3 (exterior)
- DIN 68705-3 / BFU 100
- BS 6566 Part 8 / WBP

The overlay is bonded to plywood with a weather-resistant adhesive (EN 204 class D4)

FORMALDEHYDE EMISSIONS

Determined according to EN 717-1, the formaldehyde emitted by Metsä Wood Spruce falls far below the Class E1 requirement of ≤ 0.100 ppm and also fulfils the most stringent requirements in the world (≤ 0.030 ppm). The formaldehyde emission of Metsä Wood Spruce is approximately 0.018 ppm. The thermoplastic overlay does not contain any formaldehyde.

PANEL STRENGTH PROPERTIES

Metsä Wood Spruce Flex is a CE marked product and its strength and elasticity properties are identical to the properties of standard Metsä Wood Spruce plywood. The properties are specified according to standards EN 789 and EN 1058 and can be found in the Metsä Wood Spruce Flex Declaration of Performance (DoP). The DoP documents can be downloaded from www.metsawood.com/dop.

MACHINING

Edge profiling is available on special request.

PACKING

Metsä Wood Spruce Flex panels are packed either in moisture resistant plastic wrapping or covered pallets.

PACKING QUANTITIES

PANEL SIZE mm	NUMBER OF PANELS PER PALLET BY THICKNESS				
	9	12	15	18	21
1200/1220 x 2400/2440	100	75	60	50	45

FURTHER INFORMATION

- Metsä Wood Spruce Flex Declaration of Performance (www.metsawood.com/dop)
- Metsä Wood Spruce Plywood Manual
- Metsä Wood Spruce Plywood for Construction brochure

Appendix 6. Metsä Wood Spruce Flex panel's declaration of performance (DOP)- I

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7. DECLARED PERFORMANCES

ESSENTIAL CHARACTERISTICS		PERFORMANCE								
Strength and stiffness for structural use:		Sanded Metsä Wood spruce plywood								
		Nominal thickness (mm)								
		9	12	12	15	18	21	24	27	30
		Number of plies								
		3	4	5	5	6	7	8	9	10
Characteristic bending strength (N/mm ²)		22,9	20,6	25,6	23,1	21,5	20,7	20,5	19,4	18,9
	⊥	3,0	6,5	8,1	11,1	12,3	12,7	12,4	13,4	13,7
Mean modulus of elasticity in bending (N/mm ²)		9178	8237	10235	9237	8615	8277	8205	7752	7558
	⊥	422	1363	1765	2763	3385	3723	3795	4248	4442
Characteristic compression strength (N/mm ²)		15,5	11,5	21,1	17,6	19,7	16,8	22,3	16,4	17,8
	⊥	8,5	12,5	8,9	12,4	10,3	13,2	7,7	13,6	12,2
Characteristic tension strength (N/mm ²)		9,3	6,9	12,6	10,6	11,8	10,1	13,4	9,8	10,7
	⊥	5,1	7,5	5,4	7,4	6,2	7,9	4,6	8,2	7,3
Mean modulus of elasticity in comp./tension (N/mm ²)		6212	4591	8430	7034	7886	6732	8936	6566	7119
	⊥	3388	5009	3570	4966	4114	5268	3064	5434	4881
Characteristic panel shear strength (N/mm ²)		3,5								
	⊥	3,5								
Mean modulus of rigidity in panel shear (N/mm ²)		350								
	⊥	350								
Characteristic planar shear strength (N/mm ²)		1,42	0,94	1,58	1,63	1,76	1,41	2,15	1,46	1,50
	⊥	NPD	NPD	0,81	0,87	0,64	1,18	0,39	1,12	0,72
Mean modulus of rigidity in planar shear (N/mm ²)		45,1	35,5	66,1	50,5	71,4	51,8	142,9	52,1	63,2
	⊥	NPD	NPD	20,9	29,1	24,9	37,4	24,6	41,3	35,2

|| = along the face veneer grain direction

⊥ = across the face veneer grain direction

The material values in this DoP are to be used for structural calculations with EN 1995 (Eurocode 5).

Appendix 7. Metsä Wood Spruce Flex panel's declaration of performance (DOP)- II

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ESSENTIAL CHARACTERISTICS	PERFORMANCE		
Bonding quality	Class 3 (exterior)		
Release of formaldehyde	E1		
Reaction to fire	End use condition	Minimum thickness (mm)	Class
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - with or without an air gap between the product and a substrate of class A1 or A2-s1,d0 and density of at least 540 kg/m³ - with thermal insulation of class A1 and density of at least 30 kg/m³ - without joints or with ≤ 8 mm open vertical and horizontal joints - fixed mechanically to wooden or metallic frames 	12	D-s2, d0
Water vapour permeability	872 000 μ		
Airborne sound insulation	NPD		
Sound absorption	0,10 (250 Hz – 500 Hz) 0,30 (1000 Hz – 2000 Hz)		
Thermal conductivity	0,12 W/(m K)		
Impact resistance	NPD		
Strength and stiffness under point load	NPD		
Mechanical durability	k_{mod}	According to EN 1995-1-1	
	k_{def}	According to EN 1995-1-1	
Biological durability (EN 335)	Use class 2		
Content of pentachlorophenol (PCP)	< 5 ppm		
Characteristic embedment strength	Calculated according to EN 1995-1-1: - characteristic density (ρ_k) 400 kg/m ³		
Racking resistance	Calculated according to EN 1995-1-1: - panel thickness 9-30 mm - characteristic embedment strength, see above		
Air permeability	NPD		

The material values in this DoP are to be used for structural calculations with EN 1995 (Eurocode 5).

Appendix 8. UPM ProFi deck's technical datasheet

UPM ProFi® Deck Technical Specification

MATERIAL UPM ProFi® is an environmentally innovative composite material that combines the best qualities of plastic and engineered fibers which fall as surplus by-products in self-adhesive label manufacture and processing. The material is virtually lignin free and contains no harmful chemicals.

STRUCTURE Hollow composite profile made by extrusion technology.

PROFILE DIMENSIONS	Standard mm	Standard Lengths m	Weight kg/m
Deck 150 Board	28 x 150	4.0	2.8
Rail Step	28 x 110 x 68	4.0	2.8
Cover Strip	12 x 66	4.0	0.7
Support Rail	40 x 60	4.0	1.5

Custom Lengths between 2.0 m & 6.0 m by request.
Actual length tolerances may vary from -2 mm upwards, subject to temperature. Width / thickness tolerance is +/- 1 mm.

**PHYSICAL AND MECHANICAL
PROPERTIES OF
UPM PROFI DECK 150**

Property	Test method	Typical value
Density, g/cm ³	EN ISO 1183*	1,2
Bending Strength, N/mm ²	EN 310*	13
Falling mass impact, J	EN 477*	+23°C No break (>30) -20°C No break (>15)
Surface Hardness (Brinell), N/mm ²	EN 1534*	28
Wear resistance (Taber 1000 r), mm	EN 438-2	0,16
Slip resistance	DIN 51130: 2014-02	R 10
Point load capacity	EN 1533	2600 N
Fire Class	EN 13501-1	E
Termite resistance (European termites)	EN 117	Resistant
Thermal Expansion Coefficient, 1/°C	ISO 11359-2*	4,0 x 10 ⁻⁵
Heat Transfer Coefficient, W/mK	ISO 8301	0,24
Water Absorption (24 h), %	EN 317*	< 2,5
Swelling, thickness (24 h), %	EN 317*	< 1

* Based on CEN/TS 15534 wood plastic composites (WPC).

The values above are characteristic values from quality tests and therefore not for strength calculations in the

